

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D1.3 ACTING-LLS EVALUATION REPORT

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ACTING-LLS EVALUATION REPORT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The CATALISI project aims to support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in advancing institutional transformation by designing and implementing tailored transformation pathways, supported by a set of targeted acceleration services. Within an evolving European research and innovation landscape, universities are increasingly expected to strengthen research excellence, promote Open Science and societal engagement, and ensure the long-term sustainability of research and education systems. CATALISI responds to these challenges by providing methodological, strategic, and organizational support that enables HEIs to translate policy ambitions into concrete, context-sensitive institutional changes.

Within the CATALISI project, seven Higher Education Institutions, referred to as “implementers”, committed to undertaking institutional transformation processes aligned with their local contexts and strategic priorities. These Implementers are located in seven European countries: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece), Kaunas University of Technology (Lithuania), University College Cork (Ireland), University of Gdańsk (Poland), Universitat Jaume I (Spain), LUISS Guido Carli University (Italy), and Amsterdam University Medical Center (the Netherlands). While operating in diverse national, organizational and cultural environments, all Implementers engaged with a shared methodological framework to design, implement and evaluate their transformation pathways.

Among the acceleration services deployed by CATALISI, the Acting *Living Labs* played a central role. Established under Work Package 1 as part of the “Acting-LL co-creation” service, the Acting Living Labs were conceived as time-bound, flexible and context-adaptable environments enabling HEIs to apply the Living Lab methodology to institutional transformation. Rather than functioning as permanent Living Lab infrastructures, they served as methodological acceleration mechanisms through which universities could mobilize stakeholders, experiment with participatory approaches, and co-design, implement and refine Action Plans in real institutional settings.

This deliverable presents the final evaluation of the seven Acting Living Labs, focusing on how effectively they supported institutional transformation and how the Living Lab methodology was applied in practice across the participating HEIs. The evaluation is grounded in a structured framework inspired by [ENoLL Living Lab Evaluation Framework](#) and adapted to the specific characteristics of Acting Living Labs. It provides a common analytical lens to assess methodological quality, institutional embedding, and learning dynamics, while remaining sensitive to the diversity of institutional contexts and transformation priorities.

The evaluation methodology followed an iterative, mixed-method approach aligned with the Living Lab logic of experimentation and learning. It combined two structured

surveys administered at different stages of implementation, bilateral exchanges with each Implementer, continuous monitoring through consortium and bilateral meetings, targeted mentoring and learning activities, and feedback from external evaluators. Although Task 1.5 formally started at Month 24, evaluation activities were designed as a continuous and formative process, running in parallel with the second implementation phase of the Action Plans. This approach enabled real-time reflection on methodological application, supported adaptive improvements, and strengthened institutional capacities throughout the process.

The evaluation results show that the Acting Living Labs effectively supported institutional transformation when Living Lab principles were translated into concrete organizational practices and embedded within existing governance and operational structures. Across the seven HEIs, the Living Lab methodology enabled institutions to move beyond consultation towards more participatory, reflective, and iterative modes of working. Co-design processes contributed to the development or revision of policies, frameworks, training programmes, support services and coordination mechanisms, strengthening legitimacy, ownership and institutional uptake.

Cross-case reflections reveal several recurring patterns across Implementers. Strong leadership endorsement emerged as a critical enabler, providing legitimacy to participatory approaches, and facilitating their institutional anchoring. Progress was often driven by small, cohesive implementation teams capable of translating strategic ambitions into operational actions. Methodological diversity and flexibility—combining workshops, surveys, interviews, benchmarking, prototyping and, in some cases, creative and experimental formats - allowed HEIs to address complex challenges iteratively and responsively. Embedding actions in real-life institutional contexts proved essential for feasibility and sustainability, even though it required careful management of administrative procedures, workloads, and institutional rhythms.

Stakeholder engagement displayed differentiated dynamics. Internally, the Acting Living Labs successfully mobilized researchers, academic staff, administrative units, and governance bodies, fostering shared ownership and institutional learning. External stakeholder engagement, while recognized as valuable, proved more challenging in several cases, particularly where transformation actions focused on internal governance, procedures, or research culture. This highlighted a structural tension between the ambition of broad multi-stakeholder participation and the practical requirements of institution-centered change processes.

In terms of institutional transformation achievements, the evaluation identifies tangible progress across all participating HEIs. The Acting Living Labs contributed to strengthening research culture, Open Science practices, public engagement, talent development, research support services and sustainability-oriented initiatives. In several cases, Living Lab practices initiated within CATALISI are already being

extended to other institutional initiatives, projects, or alliances, indicating early signs of longer-term institutionalization and learning.

The evaluation also highlights common challenges encountered during implementation. These include lengthy administrative and validation procedures inherent to institutional change, limited time availability of key actors involved in implementation, and difficulties in sustaining engagement—particularly among researchers and external stakeholders. Nevertheless, many HEIs mitigated these challenges by integrating Living Lab activities into existing processes, aligning them with institutional rhythms and adapting participation formats to stakeholder constraints.

Building on the evaluation findings, lessons learned among CATALISI Implementers, external expert feedback, and good practices from the wider ENoLL Living Lab network, the deliverable formulates a set of recommendations for future replicability. These recommendations emphasize the importance of embedding Living Lab practices within institutional governance cycles; investing in internal capacities for facilitation, co-creation, and stakeholder engagement; systematizing stakeholder engagement strategies; aligning Living Lab activities with academic and governance calendars; and embedding continuous monitoring and reflection mechanisms. Attention is given to strengthening external stakeholder engagement, drawing on a strategy co-created during a dedicated CATALISI side event at the Open Living Lab 2024 and fully integrated into the recommendations.

Overall, the evaluation confirms that the Living Lab methodology, when appropriately adapted, can function as a powerful accelerator of institutional transformation in Higher Education. The experience of the seven Acting Living Labs demonstrates that Living Labs are not merely a collection of tools or project activities, but a way of organizing institutional change around openness, participation, and shared ownership. When supported by leadership, capacity-building and strategic coordination, Living Lab approaches can significantly enhance HEIs' ability to navigate complexity, embed innovation and sustain long-term transformation beyond project lifecycles.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CoP	Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
DC	Dissemination and Communication
DoA	Description of Action
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	High Education Institution
LL	Living Lab
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
OS	Open Science
RCR	Responsible Conduct of Research
RI	Research Integrity
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

The CATALISI project aims to support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in advancing institutional transformation through the design and implementation of tailored transformation pathways, supported by a set of targeted acceleration services. Within an evolving European research and innovation landscape, HEIs are increasingly expected to strengthen research excellence, enhance openness and societal engagement, and ensure the sustainability of research and education systems. CATALISI responds to these challenges by equipping universities with methodological, strategic, and organizational support to design and implement context-sensitive transformation processes.

Institutional transformation within CATALISI is structured around three core domains: research careers and talent support; open science and public engagement; and sustainable research and education. These domains encompass a range of intervention areas that reflect both European policy priorities and local institutional needs (see figure 1).

FIGURE 1-THREE MAIN CATALISI DOMAINS OF INTERVENTION AND RELATED INTERVENTION AREAS

To operationalize transformation across these domains, CATALISI deploys seven complementary acceleration services, including Living Labs, design labs for transformational pathways, reinforcing human capital, predictive study on skills anticipation, a marketplace, and a community of practice. Together, these services are designed to accelerate change while strengthening collaboration, learning and alignment across European universities.

Within the CATALISI consortium, seven Higher Education Institutions, referred to as Implementers, committed to undertaking concrete institutional transformations within their respective contexts. These Implementers are located in seven European countries: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece), Kaunas University of Technology (Lithuania), University College Cork (Ireland), University of Gdańsk (Poland), Universitat Jaume I (Spain), LUISS Guido Carli University (Italy), and Amsterdam University Medical Center (the Netherlands). Each institution operates within distinct national, organisational and cultural environments, which significantly shape both the focus and the implementation of their transformation pathways. Four

Facilitator partners, APRE, EY, ENoLL and F6S, support the Implementers by providing methodological guidance, tools and expertise.

FIGURE 2- CATALISI HEIS

The CATALISI methodological framework is organized into four main and interrelated phases: exploration, co-design, implementation and evaluation. This sequencing is inspired by the Living Lab methodology and is designed as an iterative, learning-oriented process rather than a linear progression.

FIGURE 3-CATALISI METHODOLOGY

Under the implementation of WP1 “Acting-LL co-creation”, led by ENOLL, and following the establishment of the Acting Living Labs under Task 1.1 “Setting up the CATALISI Acting Living Labs”, each Implementer entered an exploration phase under **Task 1.2** “CATALISI Living Labs: Exploration stage”. This phase focused on analyzing local institutional contexts, identifying structural and cultural barriers to transformation, and examining relevant framework conditions. The results of this work were consolidated in the deliverable [D1.1 “Acting Living Labs Needs Assessment and Quadruple Helix Ecosystem”](#) which provided a comprehensive evidence base on the needs, challenges and opportunities shaping institutional transformation across the seven HEIs.

Building on the exploration findings, the project moved into the co-design phase under **Task 1.3** “CATALISI Living Labs: Co-design stage”. This phase was conducted in two iterative stages, reflecting the Living Lab principle of continuous refinement. In the first stage, Implementers collaborated with internal and external stakeholders to co-design initial versions of their Action Plans for institutional transformation. These first Action Plans defined priority intervention areas, concrete actions, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and anticipated challenges, and informed Deliverable [D1.2 “Acting Living Labs Action Plans”](#). In line with the Living Lab methodology, these Action Plans were not treated as fixed outputs but as living documents.

Implementation activities under **Task 1.4** “CATALISI Living Labs: Implementation stage” were launched following the first co-design cycle and unfolded in two phases. The first implementation phase ran until Month 24, during which Implementers tested actions in real institutional settings and gathered feedback from stakeholders. Based on insights from this first implementation cycle, the Action Plans were revised at Month 24, ensuring alignment with emerging needs, feasibility constraints and institutional learning. The second implementation phase then followed, applying the revised Action Plans, and reinforcing the iterative logic of experimentation, adjustment and consolidation.

Evaluation activities under **Task 1.5** “CATALISI Living Labs: Evaluation stage” formally started from Month 24 onwards but were designed as a continuous and formative process rather than a purely summative exercise. From December 2024, evaluation activities were carried out in parallel with the second implementation phase, allowing for real-time reflection on how the Acting Living Labs were functioning in practice. This evaluation process was closely accompanied by bilateral mentoring and feedback sessions between ENOLL and the Implementers, aimed at strengthening the application of the Living Lab methodology, clarifying methodological choices and supporting adaptive improvements where necessary. In this way, evaluation within CATALISI served both as an evidence-generation mechanism and as a capacity-building process, reinforcing methodological maturity and learning across the consortium.

This deliverable, D1.3 “Acting Living Labs Evaluation Report”, captures the results of Task 1.5 and provides a structured assessment of how the Acting Living Labs were implemented and how effectively they supported institutional transformation. It builds on earlier deliverables, particularly [D1.1 “Acting Living Labs Needs Assessment and Quadruple Helix Ecosystem”](#) and [D1.2 “Acting Living Labs Action Plans”](#), and analyses the implementation experience of all seven Acting Living Labs during the project.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows. [Chapter 2. Evaluation Framework](#) presents the evaluation framework, outlining the conceptual foundations and criteria used to assess the Acting Living Labs. [Chapter 3. Evaluation methodology](#) describes the evaluation methodology, detailing the approach adopted, the tools and data sources used, and how the evaluation was conducted alongside the implementation process. [Chapter 4. Evaluation of the Acting Living Labs Against the Six Living Lab Attributes](#) presents the evaluation of the seven Acting Living Labs against the six Living Lab attributes, including institution-specific analyses and a cross-case reflection highlighting common patterns and differences. [Chapter 5. Institutional transformation: Main Achievements Observed Across](#) synthesises the main achievements related to institutional transformation observed across the participating HEIs, highlighting key enablers and successful practices. [Chapter 6. Challenges Across CATALISI Acting Living Labs](#) discusses the main challenges encountered during the implementation of the Acting Living Labs, drawing on both the evaluation data and Implementers’ reflections. [Chapter 7. Recommendations for Future Replicability](#) presents recommendations for future replicability, outlining how HEIs can build on the CATALISI experience to sustain and scale Living Lab practices beyond the project. Finally, [Chapter 8. CONCLUSIONS](#) concludes the report by synthesising the overall findings and reflecting on the contribution of the Acting Living Labs to institutional transformation.

Through this structure, the deliverable aims not only to document results but also to generate actionable knowledge on how Living Lab methodologies can be effectively adapted to the realities of Higher Education Institutions and used as a strategic instrument for long-term institutional transformation.

2. EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

The evaluation framework provides the conceptual basis for assessing the seven Acting Living Labs established within the project. In the context of CATALISI, the Acting Living Labs represent temporary, activity-based implementations of the Living Lab methodology designed as an acceleration service to support institutional transformation within the participating HEIs. A Living Lab is an open and collaborative innovation environment in which users, stakeholders, and organizations jointly co-create, test, and validate solutions in real-life settings. Living Labs rely on principles

such as active user involvement, multi-stakeholder participation, co-creation, experimentation in real contexts, and iterative learning. These principles underpin the methodological approach applied within the CATALISI Acting Living Labs. They are not permanent Living Lab structures, but structured methodological environments where HEIs work collaboratively with users and stakeholders to co-design, test, and refine their transformation activities in real-life settings. Through these Acting Living Labs, HEIs operationalize their selected intervention areas and apply Living Lab principles, such as user involvement, multi-stakeholder engagement, real-life experimentation, and iterative learning—to advance their institutional transformation pathways.

FIGURE 4- LIVING LAB MAIN PRINCIPLES

The evaluation framework draws primarily on the ENoLL **Living Lab Evaluation Framework**, which offers a structured and internationally recognized approach for assessing Living Labs in terms of methodological quality, maturity, openness, value creation, and long-term sustainability. Using this framework ensures alignment with the principles underpinning the ENoLL Living Lab Certification Scheme and provides a robust foundation for the evaluation presented in this deliverable.

The ENoLL framework is organized around **four overarching dimensions**: Users & Reality, Tools & Methods, Impact & Value, and Stability & Harmonization. Each dimension is operationalized through concrete evaluation criteria and associated KPIs. These are summarized in [Table 1. enoll evaluation criterias](#) which outlines the key criteria used to assess the quality and maturity of Living Lab practices across the seven Acting LLs.

	CRITERION	KPI
Users & reality	User centricity	1. % of diversity of stakeholders involved as end-users in Living Lab projects and/or activities
		2. Degree of influence end-users exerts on the different phases of the innovation cycle (from informing to empowerment)
	Lifecycle & real-life	3. Degree of involvement of end-users in the different phases of the innovation cycle e.g., problem space, solution space, implementation space...)
		4. Degree of use of real-life contexts of users in the different phases of the innovation cycle
	Tools & methods	5. Degree of appropriateness of tools & methods used for the different phases of the innovation cycle
		6. Frequency of external communication & results sharing to keep end-users and external stakeholders informed and engaged
Impact & value	Co-created values	7. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation cycle
		8. Number of relevant (open) educational resources (including datasets, trainings) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders
		9. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & capacity building (learning materials & infrastructures)
	Impacts	10. Completeness & frequency of impact assessments (how often is the Living Lab monitoring different types of impacts they are generating: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, academic)
Stability & harmonization	Stability	11. % Increase in number of relationships (with a reliable partner network and customers)
		12. Level of financial sustainability based on a balanced & diversified set of fundings (structural vs. project-based) & revenue streams
		13. Number of Living Lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to new circumstances

	Harmonization & scale-up	14. % Increase in number of partners committed to scale up products/solutions/services developed by the Living Lab
		15. Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled-up
		16. Number of participation in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on harmonized Living Lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools processes or services

TABLE 1. ENOLL EVALUATION CRITERIAS

Building on this foundation, the evaluation framework also integrates the **six essential Living Lab attributes**, which constitute the core characteristics of a mature Living Lab and provide a common analytical lens for comparing the Acting LLs. These attributes are:

1. Active User Involvement
2. Multi-Stakeholder Participation
3. Multi-Method Approach
4. Orchestration
5. Real-Life Setting
6. Co-Creation

Table 2. Alignment between living lab attributes, definitions and enoll evaluation criteria below presents how each attribute is defined and how it aligns with relevant criteria and KPIs from the ENoLL evaluation framework.

BUILDING BLOCK	DEFINITION	CRITERION AND LINK TO ENOLL EVALUATION CRITERIA
Active User Involvement	A Living Lab actively involves relevant stakeholders in all activities, ensuring their feedback is captured and implemented throughout the innovation lifecycle.	Users & reality

Co-creation	In a Living Lab, values are co-created in a bottom-up approach by all relevant stakeholders, leading to higher adoption of the innovations.	Users & reality Impact & Value
Real Life Setting	A Living Lab operates in the real-life setting of end users, integrating innovations into users' daily lives instead of relocating users to test environments. 17.	Users & reality Stability & harmonization
Multi Method Approach	Each Living Lab activity is problem-driven, with the methodology selected based on expected outcomes and the relevant stakeholders who need to be involved	Users & reality Tools & methods
Orchestration	The Living Lab acts as an orchestrator within the ecosystem, facilitating connections and partnerships with relevant stakeholders	Users & reality User centricity Impact & value Co-created values
Multi Stakeholder Participation	A Living Lab adopts a holistic view, engaging stakeholders from the quadruple helix model: government, academia, private sector, and citizens.	Stability & harmonization > stability Harmonization & scale-up

TABLE 2. ALIGNMENT BETWEEN LIVING LAB ATTRIBUTES, DEFINITIONS AND ENOLL EVALUATION CRITERIA

As the Acting Living Labs established in this project do not operate as permanent Living Lab structures, they should be understood as time-bound and methodological applications of the Living Lab approach, designed to function as acceleration services supporting institutional transformation within HEIs during the project timeframe.

At this stage, the purpose of the Acting Living Labs is experimentation, learning, and capacity-building: enabling HEIs to test Living Lab principles, methods, and governance arrangements in real institutional contexts, and to assess their relevance, feasibility, and added value for long-term transformation processes. While the long-term ambition for several Implementers is to progressively institutionalise Living Lab practices beyond the project, potentially evolving towards more permanent structures or sustained Living Lab functions, this ambition lies beyond the scope of the present evaluation. The evaluation conducted in this deliverable therefore does not assess permanence or institutionalisation as an achieved outcome but rather

examines how effectively the Living Lab methodology has been applied during CATALISI as a learning and acceleration mechanism.

In this context, the ENoLL evaluation criteria and KPIs are used as a conceptual reference framework to support reflection on quality, maturity, and value creation, rather than as a formal certification or benchmarking tool. Given the methodological, experimental, and time-limited nature of the Acting Living Labs within CATALISI, the evaluation focuses on the six core Living Lab attributes, which provide a practical and context-appropriate lens for assessing methodological implementation and institutional learning.

In practical terms, the six attributes constitute the main structure of the evaluation. Rather than assessing each ENoLL dimension separately, the evaluation looks at how the Acting Living Labs:

- Engage and involve users throughout their activities (Active User Involvement).
- Mobilize and connect different stakeholder groups from within and beyond the HEI (Multi-Stakeholder Participation).
- Apply a variety of methods and tools adapted to different phases of the institutional transformation process (Multi-Method Approach).
- Coordinate and facilitate collaboration between actors, ensuring clear roles and effective facilitation (Orchestration).
- Operate in real-life contexts that are relevant to the challenges addressed by the HEIs (Real-Life Setting).
- Enable co-creation processes where different actors jointly define problems, design solutions and reflect on outcomes (Co-Creation).

The ENoLL dimensions (Users & Reality, Tools & Methods, Impact & Value, Stability & Harmonization) thus inform the interpretation of these attributes but do not constitute additional evaluation axes. For example, Users & Reality is reflected primarily through Active User Involvement and Real-Life Setting; Tools & Methods through the Multi-Method Approach; and Impact & Value through the way co-creation processes generate value for the actors involved. Aspects such as long-term stability or scale-up are acknowledged as part of the conceptual background but were not assessed as standalone criteria within this evaluation.

This integrated framework ensures that the evaluation is rigorous, transparent, and comparable across all seven Acting Living Labs, while recognizing the different institutional contexts in which they operate. It provides a solid conceptual foundation for the cross-case analysis that follows and supports a systematic assessment of how effectively the Living Lab approach has been used as a lever for institutional transformation within participating HEIs.

3. EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

The evaluation of the Acting Living Labs was conducted through an iterative, mixed-method process designed to assess both the implementation of the action plans and the extent to which the Living Lab methodology was applied by CATALISI HEIs. The approach combined structured surveys, bilateral discussions, continuous follow-up during consortium meetings, and dedicated learning activities to ensure a shared methodological foundation for the evaluation.

The evaluation process began in December 2024 with a first structured survey (See [Annex 1- Survey on the action plan implementation and the application of the living lab methodology](#)) assessing the initial application of the Living Lab methodology during the early implementation phase of the action plans. This survey provided early insights into how each Acting Living Lab was operationalized, the degree to which the six Living Lab attributes were reflected in practice, and the achievements and challenges encountered by each Implementer. It also gathered information on stakeholder engagement dynamics, the use of participatory tools and methods, and the rationale behind the revisions introduced during the first implementation cycle. Bilateral meetings with each Implementer followed, allowing for a deeper and more contextualized interpretation of the survey results, providing qualitative insight into institutional conditions, operational barriers, and methodological practices.

Throughout 2025, the evaluation was supported by continuous monitoring during monthly consortium meetings. These discussions offered regular updates on the implementation of the action plans and the adoption of Living Lab practices, enabling the evaluation to capture methodological evolution and emerging needs across the participating HEIs.

A final comprehensive survey (see [Annex 2- final Survey on the action plan implementation and the application of the living lab methodology](#)) was conducted in October 2025 following the completion of the second implementation phase. This survey provided a summative assessment of progress achieved along the institutional transformation pathways and examined the maturity reached by the Acting Living Labs in applying the six Living Lab attributes. Respondents were asked to provide concrete examples illustrating methodological application, reflect on achievements and challenges, describe how recommendations from the external evaluators within the External Acceleration Board (EAB) (T.4.6) had been integrated, and outline plans for sustaining and replicating the methodology beyond the project. The EAB, established under Task 4.6 of CATALISI, brings together external experts with complementary expertise in institutional transformation, research and innovation policy, Living Lab methodologies and higher education systems. Its role is to provide independent, strategic, and methodological feedback to the Implementers, supporting quality assurance, critical reflection and learning across the project. Implementers were therefore invited to reflect on how the EAB's external evaluations

and recommendations—particularly those related to the application of Living Lab principles and the robustness of the Action Plans—had informed revisions, implementation choices and longer-term perspectives for institutional change.

The two surveys formed the core data collection instruments of the evaluation. The first survey assessed initial experimentation with the methodology and its influence on the implementation of the action plans, while the second survey offered a consolidated perspective on methodological maturity and institutional transformation. Both surveys included structured and semi-structured questions, generating qualitative insights complemented by light quantitative signals concerning the perceived extent of methodological adoption. These quantitative elements were used descriptively to observe trends across the two implementation phases.

A key component of the evaluation methodology was the continuous mentoring and learning support provided to Implementer HEIs throughout the project by ENoLL. This support began early in CATALISI, well before the evaluation exercise, and aimed to equip HEIs with the understanding and skills needed to establish their Acting Living Labs and apply Living Lab methods in the co-design of their action plans. Through webinars, methodological guidance and the facilitation of participatory workshops carried out within the project lifetime and activities, Implementers were introduced to core Living Lab principles, which they later operationalized within their institutional transformation pathways.

As the evaluation progressed, three targeted webinars were organized in 2025 to support Implementers and ensure a coherent and robust application of the Living Lab methodology across the consortium.

The webinars were designed in response to methodological gaps and implementation challenges identified during the first phase of Action Plan implementation, as well as through continuous monitoring and feedback collected from Implementers. They were therefore closely aligned with the second implementation phase under Task 1.4 and the evaluation activities under Task 1.5, allowing learning, reflection, and assessment to progress in parallel.

Each webinar addressed a specific methodological dimension of the Living Lab approach, including practical application through case studies, external stakeholder engagement, and co-creation processes. Beyond their capacity-building function, these webinars also contributed qualitative insights to the evaluation by informing the analysis of how Implementers progressively applied and adapted Living Lab principles within their institutional transformation processes.

A first learning activity took the form of a webinar in interview and case-study format focused on the UVT Digital & Green Living Lab, hosted by the West University of Timișoara and certified by ENoLL. This session provided Implementers with concrete insights into how an established Living Lab operates over time, how stakeholder engagement is sustained beyond individual projects, and how experimentation and

learning are embedded into institutional structures. The concept note and agenda are detailed in [Annex 3- wEBINAR_CASE STUDY_uvt digital & green living lab case study](#). The discussion highlighted practical governance arrangements, facilitation choices, and mechanisms for translating co-creation outcomes into organisational change, offering a mature reference point against which Implementers could reflect on their own Acting Living Labs.

Added to this, a second webinar held online on 29 May 2025 focused on [public engagement and outreach](#) jointly organized by ENoLL and EY (within T.2.1). This session directly addressed one of the most recurrent challenges identified by Implementers during implementation: engaging external stakeholders in a sustained, meaningful and resource-efficient manner. The webinar explored participatory practices, value propositions for external actors, and practical approaches to aligning university priorities with societal needs. The detailed agenda is shown in [Annex 4- wEBINAR_Public engagement and outreach](#).

A [final learning activity](#) in 2025 (see agenda in [Annex 5- wEBINAR_co-design as driver of adaptive and learning-oriented institutions](#)), organized by ENoLL and EY on 11 December 2025 (within T.2.1), focused explicitly on co-creation and co-design as a driver of adaptive and learning-oriented institutions. This session revisited co-creation not only as a set of tools, but as a strategic capability underpinning institutional transformation.

The evaluation relied on the triangulation of multiple data sources, including survey results, bilateral exchanges with Implementers, continuous follow-up throughout the implementation phases, insights generated through structured learning activities, and feedback from external experts. In particular, the external evaluation provided by independent experts (EAB) offered a critical perspective on the extent to which the Living Lab methodology was effectively applied within the Action Plans, highlighting strengths, gaps and areas for methodological consolidation. These external comments were systematically reviewed and taken into account as part of the evaluation process, contributing to a more robust and balanced assessment of the Acting Living Labs.

This integrated approach ensured a comprehensive and validated evidence base, enabling the evaluation to compare self-reported perceptions with documented practices, identify cross-cutting patterns and recurring challenges, and assess the progressive adoption of the Living Lab methodology as an acceleration service for institutional transformation across the participating HEIs.

The consolidated evaluation results were presented and discussed with all partners during the final CATALISI General Assembly in Amsterdam on 10 November 2025, ahead of the CATALISI Final Conference. This collective discussion enabled shared validation of the findings and provided an opportunity to reflect jointly on lessons learned across implementation and evaluation.

The recommendations presented in chapter 7. [Recommendations for Future Replicability](#) build directly on this combined evidence base. In addition to the evaluation findings, they also incorporate the outcomes of a dedicated strategy on external stakeholder engagement that was co-created during a CATALISI side event [CATALISI side event 'Opening-universities to stakeholders through Living Labs for Institutional Transformation](#) organised by ENoLL at the Open Living Lab Days 2024. The workshop brought together CATALISI partners and Living Lab practitioners to jointly address challenges related to communication, alignment of priorities and resource utilization in external engagement. The resulting strategy, grounded in both the CATALISI experience and good practices from the wider ENoLL Living Lab network, has been fully integrated into the recommendations to support future replicability, sustainability, and effective external collaboration within and beyond the participating HEIs.

4. EVALUATION OF THE ACTING LIVING LABS AGAINST THE SIX LIVING LAB ATTRIBUTES

This chapter presents the evaluation of the seven Acting Living Labs established within CATALISI. As described in earlier sections, the Acting Living Labs were designed and ideated at the beginning of the project as methodological acceleration services to support the co-design and implementation of institutional transformation Action Plans. These Acting Living Labs (LLs) were conceived as time-bound, flexible and context-adaptable frameworks and approaches enabling each HEI to mobilize stakeholders, test new approaches, and structure participatory processes around their selected intervention areas.

The primary purpose of the Acting Living Labs was to apply the Living Lab methodology to identify transformation needs, co-create solutions, and implement actions in real institutional settings, thereby strengthening the HEIs' capacities for long-term change. the Acting Living Labs supported HEIs in (1) selecting and prioritizing transformation practices, (2) integrating relevant internal and external stakeholders, (3) uncovering institutional, structural, and cultural barriers, (4) co-designing Action Plans, (5) piloting and implementing interventions in real institutional settings, and (6) evaluating performance and outcomes.

Through workshops, interviews, surveys, consultations and collaborative design formats, the LLs played a central role in shaping the Action Plans developed in the first year of the project, and subsequently in accelerating their implementation during the second phase.

Building on the evaluation framework and methodological approach outlined in the previous chapter, this section assesses how effectively each Acting Living Lab applied the six core LL attributes: active user involvement, multi-stakeholder participation,

multi-method approach, orchestration, real-life setting, and co-creation. The evaluation draws on data from two dedicated surveys, bilateral discussions, continuous implementation monitoring, and insights from the external evaluation.

4.1 UCC ACTING LIVING LAB

UCC's Acting Living Lab was established from the outset of the CATALISI project to support the university's transformation pathway on research funding sustainability, institutional co-creation practices and the development of new strategic research investment models. Following the setting up of the Acting Living Lab, the team engaged in an exploration phase to analyze the local institutional context, identify barriers and enablers affecting research funding sustainability, and map the needs of relevant stakeholders. This phase provided an evidence-based foundation for understanding the complexities of UCC's internal processes and the ecosystem in which the transformation pathway would unfold.

Building on the insights generated during exploration, the Acting LL moved into the co-design phase, during which researchers, research office staff, administrative units and institutional leadership collaborated through workshops, modelling exercises and structured dialogues. These activities enabled the collective diagnosis of bottlenecks in funding processes, the refinement of the overhead model and the development of a strategic co-creation framework designed to support engaged research and sustainable financing.

The implementation of the Action Plan took place in two iterative phases, consistent with the Living Lab methodology. The first phase allowed UCC to experiment with proposed actions, assess their feasibility and gather feedback on emerging needs. Based on these insights, the Action Plan was revised before entering the second implementation phase, ensuring that interventions remained aligned with evolving priorities and contextual realities. Throughout implementation, stakeholders were regularly consulted, informed of progress, and encouraged to share feedback, reinforcing engagement and institutional ownership.

UCC had already gained experience with Living Lab methodologies in areas such as civic engagement and citizen science, and the CATALISI process further strengthened its confidence in the transformative potential of this approach. The Acting Living Lab enhanced UCC's ability to structure participatory institutional processes and confirmed the relevance of LL methods for future initiatives. The university is already applying these insights in its CityLabs project within the UNIC university alliance and contributes to the European Living Lab Hub (ELLH), which brings together European University Alliances exploring Living Lab practices at scale.

Active User Involvement

In terms of active user involvement, UCC systematically integrated user and stakeholder feedback throughout the entire lifecycle of its Acting Living Lab. From the very beginning of the project, UCC engaged internal and external stakeholders through a large workshop held on 2 August 2023, which gathered more than forty participants from across the quadruple helix, including academia, civil society, government, and private sector organizations. This event served both to introduce the CATALISI approach and to initiate the co-design phase of the Action Plan by inviting stakeholders to articulate needs, expectations and concerns related to research funding sustainability. Academic staff and researchers contributed actively to discussions on strategic investment models and the viability of new sustainability mechanisms, shaping the refinement of the Engaged Research Fund and informing the development of internal co-creation frameworks.

Following the development of the Action Plan, UCC continued to involve stakeholders by organizing an online validation workshop to present progress and collect structured feedback. Engagement was further reinforced during the MML organized by UCC in November 2024, where internal and external stakeholders were present during the event and again invited to reflect on the advancement of the work and provide additional input. Across these interactions, the Living Lab approach enabled the university to surface concerns related to funding distribution, gather proposals grounded in everyday research realities and maintain an open dialogue around its transformation pathway.

Throughout the project, UCC held ongoing discussions with both internal and external stakeholders to ensure that the evolving actions remained relevant and responsive to the needs of the ecosystem. A final stakeholder presentation is planned at the close of the project to share the outcomes of the Acting Living Lab and consolidate the collaborative relationships that developed during CATALISI.

Multi-stakeholder participation

Regarding multi-stakeholder participation, UCC drew on a broad and diverse group of stakeholders throughout its Acting Living Lab, involving a range of institutional actors across faculties and central services as well as representatives from the wider ecosystem. In total, thirty-seven stakeholders contributed to the LL activities, including 62% from academia (23 participants), 16% from civil society (six participants), 11% from industry and business (four participants) and 11% from government (four participants). This composition reflects the multidimensional nature of UCC's intervention area: sustainability in research finance, which required both internal expertise and the perspectives of national funders, research centers, government representatives and other actors operating within Ireland's research and innovation landscape.

The balance of perspectives, across sectors, levels of seniority and gender, ensured that the co-creation process remained inclusive and reflective of the range of competencies required to advance UCC's transformation pathway. Because achieving

a sustainable research funding model demands strong internal alignment before broader external partnerships can be mobilised, the UCC Acting Living Lab's emphasis on combining in-depth internal expertise with carefully targeted external input proved both appropriate and effective.

Multi-Method Approach

The multi-method approach was one of UCC's methodological strengths. The Acting Living Lab combined co-design workshops, internal consultations, surveys, financial modelling exercises and structured reflections on best practices, creating an iterative process in which early insights informed subsequent steps. This methodological diversity allowed UCC to develop a nuanced understanding of institutional needs and to design systemic improvements rather than isolated interventions.

UCC also fulfilled a dual role within the project as both implementer and evaluator. In its implementation capacity, UCC co-designed workshops with facilitating partners and visiting institutions, organized structured bilateral meetings and carried out validation workshops to test and refine emerging ideas. In parallel, UCC conducted ongoing formative evaluation activities, throughout the project, with implementing partners to constantly assess, monitor, evaluate and co-create the action plans and transformational pathways using workshops, presentations and bilateral meetings. The evaluation work was completed with a final summative assessment using a detailed survey, supported by both qualitative and quantitative data analysis, to evaluate the project through a self-assessment analysis of the partners and their perception of the project. At the beginning of the initiative, UCC performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and, in collaboration with ENoLL, conducted a SWOT analysis to inform the development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan. This combination of exploratory, participatory and analytical methods proved highly effective in guiding UCC's work, ensuring that decisions were evidence-based and grounded in the realities of the institutional and stakeholder ecosystem.

Orchestration

In terms of orchestration, UCC benefitted from a clear coordination team that ensured strong alignment between Acting LL activities and the university's institutional strategy. Regular communication loops were maintained between senior leadership, researchers, and service units, which helped secure coherence, transparency and broad stakeholder buy-in. UCC actively orchestrated engagement by inviting partners to in-person, online and hybrid workshops, although in-person formats proved particularly effective for facilitating co-creation and deeper collaboration. Stakeholders were also invited back after the co-creation of the Action Plan to provide feedback and validation, and they will be engaged again at the end of the project to review the progress achieved.

Throughout the process, UCC ensured that its senior leadership remained closely involved and informed, which contributed to sustained institutional support and strategic alignment. According to the external evaluation, UCC's Acting LL

demonstrated strong feasibility and systemic integration, with clear benefits arising from its internal coordination structures; however, further increasing the visibility and involvement of external partnerships could enhance long-term impact. Beyond ensuring high-level administrative engagement in the activities/action in UCC's Action Plan and Transformational Pathway, UCC also pushed for clear ownership of the activities to ensure sustainability, monitoring, and long-term embedding of the changes, within the university, for long-term and strategic institutional impact.

Real-Life setting

The real-life setting attribute was deeply embedded in UCC's Acting Living Lab, as all activities took place within the genuine institutional context of financial modelling, strategic planning, and day-to-day research administration. This grounding ensured that outputs were immediately actionable and that insights translated into meaningful institutional improvements. By basing every action on real organisational processes and focusing on a clearly defined and narrow intervention area, UCC was able to maximise impact and drive high-level institutional change in a targeted and effective manner.

Co-creation

Finally, co-creation played a central role throughout the Acting LL. UCC used co-creation not only to design new funding mechanisms but also to structure strategic dialogues and build internal consensus around its transformation pathway. By embedding co-creation into each stage of the process, the university strengthened collaborative practices that are likely to endure beyond the project. All actions were developed using a co-creative, multi-method approach that actively involved both internal and external stakeholders. The terminology employed across activities, such as co-creation workshops, validation sessions and co-design exercises, continually reinforced the importance of collaborative development and contributed to fostering a shared methodological language within the institution. Furthermore, the clear ownership of the actions with internal institutional stakeholders ensured that the activities were allowed to be designed, implemented, and evolve according to the direct needs of the interested parties – further ensuring the co-creative aspect of the change.

4.2 KTU ACTING LIVING LAB

KTU's Acting Living Lab was established from the beginning of the CATALISI project to support the university's transformation pathway across three priority areas: supporting talent circulation and mobility, strengthening human capital, particularly through enhanced academic writing services, and fostering public engagement and citizen science. Following the setting up of the Acting Living Lab, the team engaged in an exploration phase to analyze the local context, identify structural and cultural barriers to mobility, training, and public engagement, and map the needs of

researchers, doctoral candidates, administrative staff and external societal partners. This initial work informed the refinement of the Action Plan, which was revised iteratively based on stakeholder input and insights gathered from the first implementation cycle, enabling KTU to narrow the initial five action areas to three strategic intervention domains and strengthen the relevance and feasibility of the selected actions.

Building on this analytical groundwork, the Acting LL progressed to the co-design phase, where KTU used workshops, interviews, surveys, benchmarking exercises and consultations to collaboratively shape new mechanisms for talent development, academic writing support and enhanced public engagement. Researchers, doctoral candidates, teaching staff and service units contributed actively to identifying obstacles—for example, barriers to first-time international mobility or unmet needs in writing support—and co-designed new formats such as mobility guidelines, training plans, strengthened Writing Clinic activities, awareness-raising initiatives for citizen science, and best-practice frameworks for engaging the public in research.

KTU'S Acting Living Lab acted as a methodological umbrella that brought together internal and external stakeholders in recurring cycles of exploration, ideation, validation, and refinement.

Throughout this process, KTU adopted an iterative Living Lab logic. The first implementation phase enabled the university to test preliminary actions, gather feedback and adjust priorities; the second implementation phase integrated these revisions, allowing for more targeted and impactful activities. Stakeholders were regularly consulted to validate progress and ensure that actions remained aligned with institutional needs and the evolving context. This structured and cyclical approach strengthened KTU's capacity to co-create solutions that support mobility, enhance academic writing services, and foster meaningful engagement between the university and society.

Active User Involvement

In terms of active user involvement, KTU placed users at the core of its Acting Living Lab and ensured that their perspectives directly shaped the transformation pathway. From the outset, researchers, doctoral candidates, teaching staff and support personnel contributed to identifying gaps in academic writing support, barriers to international mobility and needs related to lifelong learning. Their input informed the definition of priorities and influenced the sequencing of actions throughout both implementation phases.

Active user engagement continued during implementation. Academic and administrative staff participated in surveys, interviews and consultations that revealed motivational and structural barriers affecting mobility, which were subsequently used to design tailored support measures. Users of the Writing Clinic, primarily researchers, doctoral candidates, and teaching staff, provided direct feedback through surveys

and interviews, enabling KTU to refine the content, accessibility and delivery of writing support services. PhD students, researchers and members of the public also participated in training sessions, workshops, and outreach activities, contributing to the shaping of citizen science and public engagement initiatives.

These continuous feedback loops ensured that users did not merely validate actions but actively steered their development, testing new approaches, refining activities and helping to ensure that proposed interventions responded authentically to real needs. This strong, iterative involvement reflects a high degree of user empowerment and demonstrates how central users were to the evolution of KTU's Acting Living Lab.

Multi-stakeholder participation

KTU's multi-stakeholder participation extended across the quadruple helix, with internal actors collaborating alongside industry partners, local organizations, and external experts to co-design elements of the talent circulation pathways, lifelong learning formats and training ecosystems. This diversity of perspectives initially enriched the Acting Living Lab and contributed to a broad understanding of both institutional and societal needs.

As the Acting Living Lab progressed, KTU observed that while the Quadruple Helix model is conceptually valuable, its practical application was not equally effective across all components of the transformation pathway. The thematic areas addressed by KTU, particularly strengthening academic writing services, improving support for international mobility, and advancing institutional talent development mechanisms, required a detailed understanding of internal structures, workflows and constraints. External stakeholders, despite their interest and goodwill, could not contribute meaningfully to such highly specialized processes, and the gap between internal and external knowledge proved too significant for sustained co-creation.

Consequently, the Acting Living Lab placed a necessary emphasis on internal stakeholders, who represent a diverse ecosystem of researchers, doctoral candidates, teaching staff, administrators and service units with the specific expertise required to drive institutional transformation. These internal actors became the primary contributors to co-creation, supported by selected external experts and representatives from national higher education and research institutions, whose perspectives remained valuable for benchmarking and broader contextual insights.

In summary, although the Acting Living Lab was designed with a Quadruple Helix logic in mind, the specialized nature of KTU's transformation goals required a more concentrated focus on internal stakeholder groups, complemented by targeted contributions from external specialists and national academic actors.

Multi-Method Approach

The multi-method approach was one of KTU's defining methodological strengths. The Acting Living Lab employed a carefully sequenced combination of interviews,

surveys, co-design workshops, benchmarking activities and prototyping exercises, with each method selected and tailored according to the expected outcomes of the specific transformation activity. For example, interviews and surveys were used at the outset to uncover unmet needs in academic writing support and to identify barriers and motivations related to international mobility. Co-design workshops then generated potential solutions, benchmarking exercises validated these ideas against external practices, and prototyping enabled the refinement of tools, guidelines, and training formats before implementation.

Each methodological choice responded directly to the nature of the challenge being addressed. For academic writing, qualitative insights were essential to understand user experiences and obstacles, while quantitative data helped identify systemic patterns. For talent circulation, mapping motivational factors and structural constraints required a combination of surveys, bilateral consultations, and iterative testing of support measures. For public engagement and citizen science, participatory workshops and training sessions allowed the Acting Living Lab to assess levels of awareness, define stakeholder roles and test outreach activities with representatives of the public.

Across all three transformation areas, KTU's methodological approach maintained a clear logic: gather robust evidence, generate solutions collaboratively, validate them with appropriate comparative insights, and refine them through testing. This deliberate and well-tailored use of methods created a truly iterative process fully aligned with the Living Lab philosophy and ensured that the outcomes of the Acting Living Lab were grounded, user-driven and institutionally relevant.

Orchestration

Orchestration at KTU was strongly supported by a clear leadership structure and a dedicated Acting Living Lab coordination team that ensured coherence across faculties, departments, and central services. The transformation process was guided by the project's core management team, whose leadership provided strategic direction and alignment with institutional priorities in internationalization, research development and public engagement. Roles and responsibilities were clearly defined from the outset, enabling efficient implementation, monitoring and iterative refinement of actions.

KTU Acting Living Lab was coordinated through regular meetings, joint planning sessions and cross-unit collaboration involving representatives from international relations, research support, academic writing services, human resources and communication units. This structure fostered coherence between different transformation areas and ensured that decisions reflected both institutional goals and user needs. Open communication channels and periodic updates helped maintain engagement among stakeholders and facilitated timely decision-making throughout the implementation process.

According to the external evaluation, KTU demonstrated strong methodological rigor and feasibility in how it orchestrated the Acting Living Lab, while also having potential to further strengthen its innovation-oriented components and expand engagement with external actors in later stages. Overall, the structured and intentional orchestration ensured consistency, accountability and strong institutional ownership, key factors that contributed to the successful advancement and sustainability of the transformation actions.

Real-Life Setting

The real-life setting attribute was consistently and effectively applied within KTU's Acting Living Lab, as all transformation activities were embedded directly into existing institutional systems, processes, and workflows. Actions were tested and implemented within authentic environments: training programmes, research support structures, academic writing services and communication processes, ensuring that outcomes were immediately actionable and grounded in the realities of everyday academic and administrative work.

Real-life institutional conditions shaped both the design and implementation of the actions. For example, the staff mobility survey and the Writing Clinic interviews were carried out with academic and administrative staff within their faculties, enabling participants to reflect on concrete experiences, constraints, and expectations. This produced realistic, context-specific insights that directly informed recommendations for improving mobility support and enhancing the Writing Clinic services. Similarly, citizen science training, lectures and outreach activities were piloted with researchers and community members, allowing KTU to test public engagement approaches with genuine audiences and observe how these practices functioned in practice.

Implementing activities in real-life settings facilitated continuous learning and adaptation. Stakeholders were able to see the immediate effects of the interventions, which strengthened ownership of the actions and deepened the institution's understanding of structural and behavioral barriers. At the same time, working within operational environments presented challenges, particularly in balancing transformation activities with regular workloads and ensuring consistent participation. However, flexible planning and clear communication helped mitigate these issues and maintain momentum.

Overall, grounding the Acting Living Lab in real institutional contexts ensured that the transformation process was realistic, responsive, and sustainable, with changes anchored in the everyday functioning of the university rather than in parallel or hypothetical processes.

Co-Creation

Co-creation was a central and defining principle of KTU's Acting Living Lab. All transformation actions were developed through collaborative processes that intentionally brought together internal and external actors to ensure that outcomes

reflected a diversity of needs, expertise and perspectives. Within the university, academic and administrative staff, researchers and doctoral candidates worked together through facilitated co-creation sessions to design actions related to international mobility support, the strengthening of the Writing Clinic and the development of citizen science and public engagement initiatives. These exchanges played a crucial role in identifying priorities, shaping feasible solutions, and aligning proposed interventions with institutional goals and operational realities.

External stakeholders, including representatives from public authorities, industry partners and civil society, contributed through participatory workshops hosted within the Acting Living Lab framework. Their insights helped situate KTU's institutional actions within broader societal and policy contexts and directly informed the development of the Public Engagement Roadmap. This ensured that KTU's transformation pathway was not only internally coherent but also responsive to societal needs and expectations.

The co-creative process cultivated mutual learning, strengthened trust across stakeholder groups and fostered shared ownership of the transformation actions. By engaging stakeholders in all phases, from exploration to co-design and validation, KTU ensured that the resulting changes were institutionally embedded, socially relevant and supported by a broad community of actors. This sustained and participatory approach demonstrates a high level of methodological maturity and positions co-creation as a lasting practice within the institution.

4.3 UJI ACTING LIVING LAB

UJI launched its Acting Living Lab at the beginning of the CATALISI project to drive a comprehensive transformation across three interconnected areas: research assessment and the recognition of academic qualifications, the institutional uptake of Open Science and Open Access practices, and the strengthening of procedures within its research ethics committees. Once the Acting Living Lab was established, the university initiated an in-depth exploration phase, examining existing policies, national requirements, and internal workflows to understand how assessment, openness and ethics operated in practice. This diagnostic work—supported by surveys, internal consultations, and the review of COARA-related developments—revealed specific bottlenecks and opportunities for improvement. These insights shaped the first version of the Action Plan, which evolved substantially as UJI progressed in the project. Feedback collected during the initial implementation cycle encouraged the university to reorganize and sharpen its actions, leading to a more focused and operational plan that extended its ambitions beyond the original formulation.

During the co-design phase, UJI brought together a broad constellation of institutional actors, researchers, technical staff, members of the quality and evaluation units, library and communication personnel, representatives from the vice-rectorates, and

ethics committee members. Through workshops, bilateral discussions, benchmarking exercises and iterative revisions, these groups collaborated to define concrete outputs such as a revised institutional framework for research evaluation, a new set of criteria and qualitative descriptors aligned with European recommendations, an “Open Access thermometer” for monitoring compliance, communication materials and training formats, and clearer guidelines to improve the functioning of ethical committees. The collaborative process ensured that the proposed measures remained both feasible and attuned to UJI’s organizational culture, gradually refining the intervention logic and creating a shared understanding of the transformation pathway.

Active User Involvement

In terms of active user involvement, UJI engaged academic staff and administrative services primarily through formal institutional structures, ensuring that users played a central role in improving Open Access procedures, contributing to training materials and refining internal guidelines across the transformation areas. Although the approach was less experimental or bottom-up than in other Acting Living Labs, the involvement of users was structured, legitimate and embedded within the university’s decision-making processes.

Institutional change at UJI necessarily requires the collaboration of a wide and diverse group of internal actors. Across all intervention areas, members of the CATALISI team played a decisive role in shaping proposals, while top management was essential in steering, revising and ultimately approving each action. Committees responsible for research assessment, Open Science and ethics provided formal validation of the outcomes, and technical staff from the Library Service, the Research Management Office, the ethics committees, and other affected units contributed substantively to the development and refinement of each product.

Although target users varied for each specific output, progress systematically depended on the coordinated contributions of many internal stakeholders. Engagement activities typically included interviews, focus groups and group meetings, enabling users to articulate needs, comment on drafts and influence final decisions. In addition, for each area of intervention, UJI established a small working group of three to four people who acted as the main driving force behind policy development. To broaden participation and capture the perspectives of the wider community, the university also conducted a large-scale institutional survey, engaging academic staff at all levels.

Multi-Stakeholder Participation

Multi-stakeholder participation, within UJI’s Acting Living Lab remained primarily internal, reflecting the nature of the transformation areas addressed, research assessment, Open Science and ethics, domains that rely heavily on institutional procedures, internal expertise, and formal governance structures. Although the initial

design of the project considered the Quadruple Helix model and external perspectives were conceptually explored during early workshops, UJI quickly realized that this framework was not well suited to the highly specialized, policy-oriented changes it sought to introduce. The thematic focus of the Acting Living Lab required detailed knowledge of internal processes, evaluation criteria and regulatory obligations, creating a natural gap between internal and external stakeholders that limited opportunities for meaningful external participation.

Given this context, internal stakeholders, academic staff, quality and evaluation units, ethics committee members, technical personnel, and senior management, became the primary actors throughout the process. These groups represent a wide and heterogeneous community with distinct responsibilities and expertise, and their involvement was essential for ensuring that the proposed changes were relevant, feasible and institutionally embedded. External contributions were nonetheless included at key moments: UJI engaged individuals from national policy contexts and the broader higher education and research ecosystem, whose insights provided valuable benchmarking and contextual alignment, even if they were not directly involved in regular Acting Living Lab activities.

In summary, while the Quadruple Helix ideal remains conceptually valuable, the specificity of UJI's transformation pathway required a predominantly internal focus, complemented by targeted input from external experts and national representatives. This configuration ensured that the Acting Living Lab remained closely aligned with institutional priorities while still benefiting from broader sectoral perspectives.

Multi-Method Approach

UJI applied a multi-method approach that combined consultations, internal workshops, surveys, interviews, and iterative validation cycles. These methods were well suited to the governance-focused nature of the transformation areas, even if they were not always explicitly framed as Living Lab techniques. Each area of change required a distinct methodological configuration, reflecting the complexity of research assessment reform, Open Science implementation and the improvement of ethical review procedures.

The overarching logic guiding UJI's approach was to build a comprehensive understanding of institutional concerns, workflows, and internal dynamics before proposing solutions. To do this, the Acting Living Lab drew on both quantitative tools—such as surveys on research assessment and Open Science—and qualitative tools, including interviews, focus groups and structured dialogues with committees and technical services. Quantitative data allowed UJI to detect patterns and levels of compliance, while qualitative insights helped reveal motivations, challenges, and operational barriers.

This combination of methods supported a grounded and evidence-informed refinement of the Action Plan across multiple cycles. It enabled the university to align

its interventions with real needs, to test emerging proposals with the relevant institutional actors and to ensure that the final outputs were both feasible and contextually coherent.

Orchestration

Orchestration within UJI's Acting Living Lab relied on a distributed governance structure involving multiple committees, commissions, and technical units. This configuration ensured strong institutional alignment, as each action was connected to the formal bodies responsible for research assessment, Open Science, or research ethics. However, the dispersion of responsibilities also made it more difficult to articulate a unified Acting Living Lab architecture, a point noted in the external evaluation, which suggested that closer integration across these structures could further strengthen methodological coherence.

Leadership played a central role in sustaining the transformation process. The Vice-Rector for Research provided overarching strategic direction, ensuring consistency between the Acting Living Lab activities and the institution's broader research and innovation agenda. In parallel, the appointment of the Academic Director for Open Science and Research Integrity created a pivotal link between the project and the university's governance ecosystem. This role made it possible to maintain continuous dialogue with the relevant committees and commissions, facilitate the negotiation of new measures and ensure that each proposed change was embedded within the appropriate institutional structures.

This configuration enabled UJI to stay closely connected to the diverse actors essential for institutional transformation. While coordination mechanisms varied depending on the nature of each intervention and the specific KPIs involved, the combination of distributed governance and dedicated academic leadership provided the stability and legitimacy required to advance the transformation pathway.

Real-Life Setting

The real-life setting attribute was strongly embedded in UJI's Acting Living Lab, as all actions were implemented directly within existing institutional structures such as assessment committees, training programmes and research support units. Rather than creating parallel processes, the university worked through the committees and commissions responsible for research evaluation, Open Science, and ethics, ensuring that transformation efforts took place within the actual environments where decisions, assessments and procedures are carried out. Maintaining continuous dialogue with colleagues in these bodies allowed the Acting Living Lab to understand real constraints, test proposals in authentic operational settings and adjust actions based on practical feedback. This close engagement with institutional realities was essential for ensuring that the resulting changes were feasible, meaningful, and capable of being sustained beyond the duration of the project.

Co-Creation

Co-creation at UJI took shape primarily within governance processes, where institutional tools, criteria and guidelines were refined collaboratively through the involvement of committees, technical services, and leadership structures. While the university initially explored co-design sessions that included both internal and external actors, this approach was later adjusted in favor of more focused internal processes, which proved more effective for advancing the highly specialized institutional changes at stake.

Within the university, co-creation was reflected in joint planning sessions, iterative discussions and collaborative drafting activities involving researchers, administrative units, vice-rectorate representatives and committee members. Although these interactions did not always carry the explicit label of “co-creation workshops,” they fulfilled the same function: gathering diverse institutional perspectives, negotiating priorities, and shaping concrete outputs collectively. This mode of collaboration strengthened internal alignment and ensured that each action was grounded in shared understanding and institutional legitimacy. Overall, UJI’s Acting Living Lab demonstrates a strong capacity for internal collaborative governance, even if opportunities remain to make the co-creation dimension more explicit and to explore greater engagement with external actors in future iterations.

4.4 UG ACTING LIVING LAB

UG’s Acting Living Lab unfolded through a structured sequence of phases that guided its transformation efforts across two main areas: Public Engagement and Outreach to Society, and Sustainability in Campus Operations. The process began with a thorough exploratory phase, during which the university examined its institutional context, identified local needs, and mapped relevant stakeholders from the Faculty of Economics, the business community and the school sector. These initial analyses highlighted gaps in collaboration, public engagement, and sustainable campus practices, providing the basis for the first version of the Action Plan.

During the co-design phase, UG brought together academic staff, students, business representatives and secondary-school educators to collaboratively refine the planned actions. This phase enabled the development of practical interventions grounded in real institutional and societal needs. The Acting Living Lab was used to design and test several activities, including collaboration between students and companies for the preparation of commissioned theses addressing concrete market needs; bilateral discussions on addressing the challenges for intellectual property in academic expertise given to companies; cooperation with high schools and teachers through awareness-raising events and sustainability-related activities; and the creation of a Citizen Science Lab intended to better understand business expectations and the potential contribution of academic expertise to local socio-economic

challenges. Educational and communication materials supporting public engagement were also developed and systematically tested with relevant user groups.

As implementation progressed, UG relied on continuous dialogue and feedback loops to assess the relevance of ongoing actions and adjust them where necessary, both with internal (e.g. Rector Office, data stewards) and external stakeholders (e.g. secondary schools, local authorities, companies). Activities took place in real-life settings- classrooms, company environments, community partnerships and university structures-ensuring that insights collected during interactions directly shaped refinements in procedures and outputs. This iterative process reinforced the connection between the university and its external ecosystem while embedding engagement practices more deeply within institutional routines.

Toward the end of the implementation period, UG expanded the scope of its Action Plan by introducing an additional activity focused on the integration of students participating in new international and joint-diploma programmes, including those within the SEA 2.0 consortium. This adjustment emerged naturally from the Acting Living Lab process, as stakeholders identified the need to strengthen the social sustainability dimension of campus operations and to support the university's increasing internationalisation. The new action complemented existing priorities and reinforced the broader transformation pathway including all the sustainability dimensions.

Overall, UG's Acting Living Lab provided a coherent framework that enabled the university to move from exploration to co-design, implementation and refinement while maintaining a strong connection to real institutional practices and societal expectations while meeting the strategic goals. Also, this framework served as a reference point for updating the university strategy and objectives for the next years. The process allowed UG to prototype and consolidate solutions that are both meaningful for the university community and responsive to the regional context in which it operates.

Active User Involvement

In terms of active user involvement, UG mobilised a wide range of users throughout the development and implementation of its actions. Students, teachers, researchers, commercialization-oriented internal bodies, companies, and civil society actors were continuously engaged and contributed to shaping the content and direction of the transformation activities. Their inputs played a decisive role in refining educational resources, improving tools linked to intellectual property and validating the design of the Citizen Science Lab, ensuring that each action responded to real needs.

Companies were closely involved through focus groups and consultations, both to optimise communication processes related to the preparation of commissioned theses and to provide insights into potential adjustments to academic programmes. High-school students and teachers participated in workshops and contributed

feedback that strengthened the development of pedagogical toolkits, while UG's own students and teaching staff took part in activities designed to foster integration and community-building. The Rector's Office and the Library were engaged in work related to Open Science, ensuring institutional alignment, and the Dean of the Faculty contributed to validating the circularity initiative on book sharing. Univentum Lab (spin-off company owned by UG), as a key partner, supported intellectual property-related activities by acting as both presenter and consultant during events and webinars together with the representatives of the Experts Advisory Board consisting of managers of companies.

Across all groups, feedback was consistently positive. Companies particularly appreciated the opportunity to validate practices developed in cooperation with the academic community and the university's spin-off company, while high schools reported strong interest and satisfaction with the collaboration and willingness to continue this in future. This sustained and meaningful involvement underscores the centrality of users in shaping UG's Acting Living Lab and highlights the strength of UG's participatory approach.

Multi-Stakeholder participation

UG demonstrated strong multi-stakeholder participation, engaging actors from the private sector, education, civil society, and academia throughout the Acting Living Lab process. Industry partners collaborated closely during the preparation of commissioned theses and participated actively in events such as Intellectual Property Week, providing practical insights into business needs and validating proposed practices. Their involvement represented roughly one-fifth of all stakeholder engagement and played an important role in shaping UG's outreach and applied research activities.

School communities-including both students and teachers-also contributed significantly, particularly in the development and testing of educational toolkits and sustainability-related activities. Although government was not directly involved, high schools can be understood as part of the public sector through their connection to local authorities, and their participation amounted to approximately 10% of all stakeholder engagement. Civil society organisations contributed an additional 10%, notably through feedback sessions on intellectual property topics and through participation in outreach initiatives.

The academic community represented the largest stakeholder group, accounting for around 60% of involvement. This included researchers, teaching staff, administrative units and management bodies who collaborated on operational tasks and co-designed the new activities introduced through the Acting Living Lab. Their central role ensured that proposed actions aligned with UG's institutional structures, complemented existing strategies, and could be realistically embedded into university routines.

Together, these diverse contributions enriched the Acting Living Lab ecosystem and provided UG with a wide range of perspectives, strengthening the relevance and feasibility of the proposed institutional transformation activities.

Multi-Method Approach

The multi-method approach was a strong dimension of UG's Acting Living Lab. The university combined co-design workshops, benchmarking, prototyping, focus groups and consultations to iteratively refine its tools, processes and engagement activities in a few feedback loops and cycles of updates. These methods were applied in a structured sequence that allowed stakeholders to influence outputs at several points in the development cycle.

For the establishment of the Citizen Science Lab (CSL), UG began with co-design sessions and a review of best practices gathered through MML exchanges and desk research. This exploration phase informed the first prototype of the CSL, which outlined its intended functions and operating principles. The prototype was subsequently validated with central units such as the Centre for Sustainable Development and further refined through consultations with the Rector's Office, ensuring institutional coherence and operational feasibility.

A similarly multi-layered approach was used for activities related to intellectual property. Workshops were combined with presentations, discussions and idea-gathering exercises that enabled participants to co-design elements of agreement between academia and industry. For the preparation of theses addressing company challenges, UG employed interviews, focus groups, brainstorming sessions, and repeated feedback loops. These dialogues involved companies in the early stages and later engaged internal units responsible for monitoring thesis preparation, allowing the process to evolve in response to practical needs and real-world constraints.

Other outreach and engagement events applied lighter versions of this mixed-methods approach, but still incorporated elements of consultation and validation. Overall, UG's use of multiple complementary methods supported a rich and iterative development process, ensuring that actions were grounded in evidence, aligned with user needs and continuously improved through interaction with stakeholders.

Orchestration

Orchestration in UG's Acting Living Lab relied on a hybrid governance model that combined the work of a dedicated core team with the engagement of key institutional structures. The core team of four people acted as the design and facilitation unit, coordinating activities across the different transformation areas, and ensuring continuity throughout the process. Their role included planning, stakeholder engagement, methodological guidance and monitoring the progression of each action. This helped to keep track of the implementation of actions and carry out tasks

on time. This coordination in a small team was the key to successful implementation of all tasks while involving multiple stakeholders and methods.

Implementation, however, depended heavily on established university bodies that brought operational authority and thematic expertise. Central offices and the Dean of the Faculty of Economics provided strategic alignment and oversight, ensuring that proposed activities were consistent with institutional priorities. Univentum Lab, a spin-off of the University of Gdańsk, played a crucial role in orchestrating intellectual property-related activities by advising on content, presenting at events and supporting the development of guidelines. The Faculty's Committee for Theses was also central, particularly in validating and coordinating the process of preparing commissioned theses for companies, thereby connecting academic processes with external business needs.

This distributed orchestration model enabled UG to leverage existing institutional strengths while introducing new collaborative practices through the Acting Living Lab. The external evaluation highlighted the effectiveness of this structure but also noted that some actions risked becoming overly procedural or descriptive, suggesting that future cycles could benefit from strengthening methodological ambition and more explicitly articulating the Living Lab dimensions within the governance process.

Overall, orchestration at UG combined strategic leadership, operational expertise, and hands-on facilitation, creating the conditions for coherent implementation and sustained collaboration across university units and external partners.

Real-Life Setting

The real-life setting was one of UG's distinctive strengths. Many activities were implemented directly within authentic environments such as classrooms, laboratories, and company workplaces, allowing tools and processes to be tested under real conditions. Collaborations with businesses enabled students to work with genuine case studies and contribute to solving practical problems, while interactions with schools provided meaningful opportunities to test educational resources with teachers and pupils. Although some delays occurred due to internal administrative procedures, the practical application of the actions generally progressed without major obstacles.

Not all activities were fully implemented during the project period; several were conceived as pilot tests to assess their feasibility and usefulness as future initiatives. Nevertheless, the actions that took place in real-life settings already produced tangible outcomes. Cooperation with companies resulted in an increased number of theses grounded in real business challenges and preparing the updates for theses supervisors and university bodies to strengthen the academia-industry connections. Intellectual Property Week is expected to stimulate further collaboration between academia and industry, potentially increasing the use of services offered by Univentum Lab and the Centre for Analyses and Expertise. The launch of the Citizen

Science Lab is anticipated to foster more interdisciplinary project proposals and, over time, to contribute to securing external funding and fill in the gap of interdisciplinary research inside the university bringing the synergy effects to many research disciplines. The book-sharing initiative strengthens sustainability and circularity efforts within the university, while outreach events for high schools are likely to expand UG's portfolio of public engagement activities and deepen connections with external stakeholders.

Overall, embedding actions in real environments enabled UG to observe how ideas functioned in practice, adjust activities based on genuine feedback and lay the groundwork for sustained, long-term engagement with societal actors.

Co-creation

Co-creation played an important role in UG's Acting Living Lab, particularly in the development of educational tools, citizen science activities and mechanisms for collaboration with external partners. In the area of university–industry cooperation, co-creation was used to shape communication processes between academia and companies, ensuring that expectations around study programmes and commissioned theses were clearly defined and mutually understood. This collaborative approach enabled both sides to jointly refine procedures and develop models that better support applied learning and problem-solving.

Co-design methods also guided the early development of the Citizen Science Lab. Stakeholders worked together to articulate the Lab's purpose, define its core functions and establish initial operating principles. This collective process provided a shared foundation for the Lab's future implementation and helped ensure that its objectives aligned with both institutional priorities and the needs of external partners.

Through these activities, co-creation contributed to strengthening dialogue, improving the relevance of proposed solutions and building shared ownership of the transformation actions.

4.5 AUMC ACTING LIVING LAB

AUMC's Acting Living Lab was structured around a transformation pathway aimed at strengthening Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) and fostering a positive research culture across the Amsterdam UMC and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. From the outset, the Acting Living Lab guided a systematic process through which researchers, supervisors, integrity coordinators, policy makers and educational experts jointly examined existing practices, identified gaps in research integrity training and co-developed a sustainable RCR learning pathway. The initial exploratory phase focused on mapping current educational offerings, assessing institutional facilities and procedures supporting research integrity, and identifying the needs of PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers, and senior academics. These insights

informed the co-design of a series of educational interventions—including redesigned RCR courses, the development of MPowering Responsible Supervision training, qualitative and quantitative studies on research culture and the development of a theatre play on research culture—each of which was iteratively tested, refined and aligned with institutional priorities. Through this process, the Acting Living Lab became a structured environment where empirical research, participatory co-creation and reflective dialogue were combined to embed RCR principles more deeply into everyday academic practice and to stimulate long-term cultural change.

Active User Involvement

Active user involvement was a defining feature of AUMC's Acting Living Lab. Researchers, clinicians, PhD candidates, supervisors, integrity coordinators and policy officers were engaged throughout the entire process, from the early exploration of research culture challenges to the validation of newly developed tools and learning pathways. Their contributions shaped the identification of cultural barriers, revealed underlying norms influencing daily research practices and informed the priorities of the transformation pathway.

Users participated in several qualitative and quantitative research studies that examined perceptions of Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR), supervisory roles and broader cultural dynamics within the institution. These insights formed the empirical backbone of the Acting Living Lab. In addition, AUMC organized participatory workshops and repeated consultation meetings over multiple years, enabling experts, educators, and policy actors to co-develop interventions, refine draft materials and test emerging ideas.

A particularly innovative form of user involvement was the use of theatre-based sessions, which provided a creative and safe environment for participants to explore dilemmas, surface implicit assumptions and open dialogue about sensitive aspects of research culture. These sessions translated lived experience into shared reflection, helping the institution recognize and articulate challenges that are often difficult to discuss through traditional methods.

Through these iterative and immersive processes, users were not only consulted but positioned as co-authors of the transformation. Their lived experiences anchored the Acting Living Lab in the real conditions of research life and ensured that the resulting interventions were both meaningful and grounded in institutional reality.

Multi-Stakeholder participation

Multi-stakeholder participation within AUMC's Acting Living Lab was centered primarily on actors from within the academic and clinical research environment. Given that the transformation pathway focused on strengthening Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) and improving research culture, the most relevant stakeholders were those directly embedded in the institution's research ecosystem. As a result, early-

career researchers, PhD candidates, postdoctoral fellows, senior academics, supervisors, integrity coordinators, educational designers and policy staff formed the core of the Living Lab community.

This concentration on internal stakeholders was both intentional and appropriate. The cultural and procedural changes targeted by the Acting Living Lab—such as revising RCR training, enhancing supervision practices, improving integrity procedures, and stimulating open discussions about research culture—required deep engagement with individuals who shape and experience these processes daily. External experts contributed selectively, particularly to specialized components such as training design, theatre methodologies and integrity policy development, but the substantive work depended on building strong internal alignment.

By bringing together researchers at different career stages, clinicians involved in scientific work, support staff, educators and policy actors, the Acting Living Lab created a rich internal ecosystem capable of examining institutional culture from multiple perspectives. This diversity within academia helped illuminate the complexity of research practices and ensured that the solutions developed were grounded, relevant and collectively owned.

Multi-Method Approach

The multi-method approach was one of the most innovative aspects of AUMC's Acting Living Lab. The university combined empirical research, creative facilitation techniques, thematic workshops and structured consultations to explore research culture and develop interventions that were both evidence-informed and deeply reflective. All actions and learning activities were grounded in input and research conducted within the institution, allowing the Living Lab to build directly on the experiences and needs of its researchers, supervisors and support staff.

Empirical studies, including interviews, surveys and qualitative cultural analyses, provided a rigorous foundation by capturing how researchers at different career stages perceive integrity, supervision and daily research pressures. These findings informed the design of targeted interventions such as revised RCR training modules and the MPowering Responsible Supervision programme.

Creative methods, particularly theatre-based formats, played a distinctive role in AUMC's approach. Through embodied scenarios and dramatized dilemmas, participants were able to explore sensitive research integrity issues in a safe, engaging and emotionally resonant environment. This method helped surface implicit norms, expose tensions within research practices and stimulate open, reflective dialogue that would otherwise be difficult to achieve.

Alongside these innovative elements, AUMC organized thematic workshops, expert sessions and repeated consultation rounds with policy specialists, educators and

integrity officers. These iterative exchanges allowed the team to refine interventions, align them with institutional structures and ensure long-term relevance.

Taken together, the combination of empirical inquiry, creative facilitation and structured dialogue created a powerful methodological ecosystem that enabled AUMC to connect research culture analysis with practical capacity-building and institutional change.

Orchestration

Orchestration within AUMC's Acting Living Lab was notably strong and was anchored in the newly established RIOS Centre (Research Integrity and Open Science Amsterdam). The creation of this centre provided a clear and stable governance structure for coordinating the transformation pathway, ensuring continuity across activities and integrating the various networks that emerged during the project. The RIOS Centre functions as the institutional hub for research culture work: it brings together supervisors, integrity officers, educators, policy makers and researchers; organises thematic meetings; and will continue to support the development and implementation of research culture initiatives beyond the project's duration.

This organizational model enabled AUMC to orchestrate the Acting Living Lab in a coherent and sustainable manner. The center facilitated coordination across faculties and departments, aligned interventions with institutional priorities and created a space where different actors could collaborate on research integrity challenges. The external evaluation praised this alignment and emphasized the strength of embedding the Acting Living Lab within a permanent institutional structure. At the same time, it noted that AUMC could further enhance its transformative potential by expanding engagement with external actors in future cycles, particularly given the broader societal relevance of research integrity and research culture issues.

Overall, orchestration at AUMC successfully balanced strategic leadership, institutional alignment, and operational coordination, positioning the Acting Living Lab as a catalyst for long-term cultural change.

Real-Life Setting

The real-life setting was intrinsically embedded in all activities of AUMC's Acting Living Lab, as interventions took place directly within the day-to-day environments of research and academic practice. Workshops, supervision trainings, consultations and theatre-based sessions were conducted in the same operational contexts where research is performed, supervised, and evaluated. This close integration ensured that insights generated through the Acting Living Lab were immediately applicable, relevant, and grounded in the lived experiences of researchers and supervisors.

A distinctive feature of AUMC's approach was that implementation, evaluation and study of the actions occurred simultaneously. The team continuously tested interventions in real conditions, whether through piloting revised RCR courses,

observing supervisory practices, or running theatre sessions, and used these observations to refine and strengthen subsequent iterations. This dynamic created an ongoing feedback loop between practice and learning, characteristic of a mature Living Lab environment.

Challenges nonetheless emerged, particularly the limited availability of researchers, who face heavy workloads and competing responsibilities. Engaging them consistently required flexibility, targeted communication, and alignment with existing obligations. However, once reached, researchers generally recognized the relevance and value of the initiatives. Their willingness to reflect on dilemmas, share experiences and contribute to improvements underscored the importance of strengthening a culture of Responsible Conduct of Research within the institution.

Overall, embedding actions in real research settings enabled AUMC to generate authentic insights, tailor interventions to actual needs and foster cultural change that resonates with the everyday realities of academic life.

Co-creation

Co-creation was a central pillar of AUMC's Acting Living Lab, particularly in the development of the Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) learning pathway and the shaping of institutional guidelines connected to research integrity and supervision. The process brought together researchers, supervisors, integrity coordinators, policy officers, educators and clinical staff in repeated cycles of dialogue, reflection and joint design. Through this collaborative engagement, participants were able to collectively articulate needs, negotiate priorities and co-produce solutions that reflected the diversity of perspectives within the institution.

AUMC organized a wide range of participatory formats—including thematic meetings, co-design workshops, theatre sessions and conferences—that enabled stakeholders to work together and openly reflect on the norms, pressures and dilemmas that influence research culture. The creative and reflective nature of these activities helped build shared understanding, surface implicit assumptions, and strengthen collective ownership of the resulting interventions. The co-development of the RCR learning pathway illustrates the depth of this engagement: it emerged through iterative exchanges between educators, researchers and integrity specialists, each contributing expertise and lived experience.

This sustained participatory process positions AUMC's Acting Living Lab as one of the more innovative examples within the consortium. By combining empirical inquiry with creative facilitation and collaborative design, the LL fostered a culture of shared responsibility for research integrity and created a foundation for continued institutional learning and cultural change.

4.6 LUISS ACTING LIVING LAB

LUISS' Acting Living Lab supported a transformation pathway centered on three major institutional priorities: strengthening research excellence through talent circulation and mobility; mainstreaming Open Science and the digitalization of research; and enhancing the university's Third Mission and public engagement activities. From the beginning of the project, the Acting Living Lab provided a structured and iterative environment through which LUISS could explore institutional needs, analyze barriers, and co-design solutions with the direct involvement of academic staff, administrative services, governance bodies, and external experts.

Following the initial set-up of the Acting Living Lab, LUISS conducted an exploration phase that included desk research on EU standards for Open Science, stakeholder mapping, and internal assessments on talent mobility, research support practices, and awareness of the Third Mission. These activities generated a shared understanding of the institutional context and clarified gaps in internal procedures, communication flows, and policy frameworks.

The co-design phase built on this groundwork by engaging researchers, department heads, the Research & Third Mission Office, the Library, and other administrative units in the development of revised action plans structured around short-, medium- and long-term goals. Workshops, consultations, and surveys enabled stakeholders to shape the design of new initiatives—such as updated policies for ERC and MSCA talent attraction, Open Access and Open Science practices, and enhanced mechanisms for faculty involvement in public engagement. This iterative work ensured that action plans were grounded in institutional realities and aligned with European research standards.

Throughout the implementation phase, LUISS applied the Acting Living Lab approach across real institutional workflows. Monthly communications and seminars supported talent circulation and attraction, while updated webpages, training sessions and internal research evaluation criteria strengthened the uptake of Open Science practices. In parallel, engagement activities and training enhanced the maturity of Third Mission initiatives. The revision of action plans in December 2024 reflected insights from the first wave of implementation, allowing LUISS to refine priorities and reinforce its ambition to become a leading institution in research excellence, Open Science, and societal engagement.

Active User Involvement

Active user involvement was largely applied, with both academic staff and administrative personnel contributing meaningfully to the design and refinement of research support formats, training resources and communication materials. Their feedback was not merely consultative but directly informed adjustments to services and helped shape the direction of several transformation actions. For example, a dedicated survey and accompanying report were developed to assess awareness and understanding of the Third Mission, providing valuable insights that guided subsequent activities. Overall, user involvement was sustained, substantive and

instrumental in ensuring the relevance, feasibility, and long-term uptake of the proposed measures.

Multi-Stakeholder participation

Multi-stakeholder participation involved a broad range of internal actors and a selected group of external partners, particularly within activities related to the Third Mission and public engagement. This approach enabled LUISS to connect internal expertise with societal stakeholders and to position academic work within broader societal dialogues. While the institutional transformation process was primarily driven by researchers and administrative staff, targeted efforts were made to engage actors from the wider ecosystem—especially in areas such as research excellence applications, talent circulation, and community-facing initiatives. Although external participation was meaningful, it was primarily concentrated on specific components of the action plan.

Multi-Method Approach

The multi-method approach was well structured, combining surveys, desk research, consultations, and internal workshops. This methodological mix enabled LUISS to triangulate insights, validate assumptions and refine services iteratively across the different phases of the transformation process. Multiple forms of evidence were used to guide decision-making, ensuring that actions were grounded in both institutional realities and broader sectoral trends. For example, surveys and desk research were systematically incorporated into the action plan to assess existing practices, identify gaps and benchmark against European standards. This diversity of methods enhanced the quality, robustness and long-term sustainability of the transformation measures.

Orchestration

Orchestration was strong, with a dedicated coordination team ensuring alignment and communication across university structures. The process was led by the Research and Third Mission Office, which worked closely with other units according to their roles and areas of expertise, creating a structured but flexible model of governance. Communication mechanisms—including internal newsletters and regular updates—helped maintain visibility of the activities, support engagement and ensure that progress was shared across the institution. This coordinated approach enabled effective cross-unit collaboration, strengthened collective ownership of the transformation pathway, and ensured continuous monitoring of progress, thereby supporting the institutional embedding and sustainability of the actions developed.

Real-Life Setting

The real-life setting attribute was clearly present, as transformation actions were implemented directly within existing institutional processes, service routines and engagement structures. Activities were embedded in authentic operational

environments, enabling faculty, administrative staff and governance bodies to interact with new tools and procedures as part of their regular workflows. For example, enhanced support for ERC and MSCA applications was delivered through the established research support structure, allowing LUISS to test new procedures, gather real-time feedback and identify the actual needs of staff and researchers. Implementing actions in real-life settings made it possible to observe barriers, enablers, and behavioural responses as they unfolded, leading to more realistic adjustments and increasing the likelihood of long-term institutional uptake.

Co-creation

Co-creation played a significant role in the refinement of tools, guidelines, and services, with internal stakeholders actively shaping the design and implementation of key transformation actions. Through consultations, workshops and iterative feedback loops, researchers, administrative staff and governance units collectively contributed to improving procedures, support formats and engagement mechanisms. This collaborative approach strengthened mutual understanding across units, fostered cross-functional cooperation and ensured that the resulting actions were closely aligned with the actual needs and priorities of the university. By embedding co-creation throughout the process, LUISS reinforced shared ownership and increased the likelihood of long-term institutional uptake of the measures developed.

4.7 AUTH ACTING LIVING LAB

AUTH's Acting Living Lab supported a transformation pathway centered on research assessment and recognition of qualifications, the digitization of research through MOOCs, and the mainstreaming of Open Science and sustainable research practices. The adoption of the Living Lab methodology within CATALISI was facilitated by AUTH's previous experience with Living Lab experimentation and participatory approaches, developed through earlier institutional initiatives and European projects, and shared within the consortium, including during the Mutual Mentoring Lab (MML) in January 2024.

Following the establishment of the Acting LL, AUTH launched an exploration phase that involved reviewing existing policies and procedures, mapping qualification and career progression processes, and identifying gaps related to Living Lab and Citizen Science participation. This initial analytical work was essential for understanding the institutional landscape and provided a foundation for designing a certification and accreditation framework tailored to AUTH's structures.

Building on this groundwork, the co-design phase engaged researchers, administrative staff, educators, the Library, the Technology Transfer Office and governance actors in the development of targeted actions. These included revising policies for qualification recognition, integrating MOOCs into the Medical School

curriculum, and creating mechanisms for fair data and IP sharing. Workshops, training activities and iterative consultations helped refine these actions and ensure their feasibility within AUTH's operational context.

Throughout implementation, the Acting Living Lab served as a structured collaboration environment that enabled AUTH to test actions within real institutional workflows—such as embedding a new lecture on data sharing in the Medical School, delivering MOOCs-related training for professors, and piloting procedures for data and IP management. This iterative and participatory approach ensured continuous alignment across faculties, strengthened cross-unit collaboration and reinforced AUTH's broader ambition to enhance research culture, transparency, and institutional recognition processes.

Active User Involvement

AUTH demonstrated strong active user involvement, with meaningful engagement from researchers, administrative units, and early-career academics. Their input played a central role in shaping training formats, refining Open Science procedures, and informing recognition mechanisms. Across the implementation process, users were engaged through working group discussions, consultations, and structured feedback sessions, contributing directly to identifying priorities and co-developing solutions.

In addition to internal engagement, AUTH also involved the broader Living Lab community (including students, university stakeholders and representatives from the local authority) through co-creation workshops and collaborative design activities. These external perspectives helped ensure that the approaches developed were relevant, practical, and aligned with local needs as well as with the wider innovation ecosystem.

As a result, the transformation actions were more widely understood and embraced, fostering a sense of shared ownership, and supporting the long-term sustainability of the changes within the department and across the wider university.

Multi-Stakeholder Participation

AUTH demonstrated broad multi-stakeholder participation, engaging actors from across the Quadruple Helix—including academia, public authorities, private-sector partners, and community stakeholders. This diversity contributed to a more systemic and inclusive transformation process. Academia represented the largest group (approximately 60%), with academic staff, administrative personnel, librarians, legal officers, researchers, and students participating in co-design workshops, surveys and prototyping activities. Their involvement ensured that the actions were grounded in real teaching, research and service needs.

Government and public authorities (around 15%) contributed to aligning the transformation with institutional and regional priorities, particularly in areas such as recognition mechanisms, Open Science and strategic planning. The private sector

(about 15%) engaged through the Living Lab network, offering perspectives on innovation processes, collaboration models and data management practices relevant to Open Science and intellectual property. Civil society and community stakeholders (approximately 10%) provided user-centered insights that strengthened the societal relevance and accessibility of the tools and procedures developed.

This diversified and participatory engagement fostered balanced representation, strengthened shared ownership across stakeholder groups and supported the creation of transformation actions that are both institutionally embedded and responsive to broader societal needs.

Multi-Method Approach

AUTH applied a sophisticated multi-method approach that combined surveys, benchmarking, co-design workshops and elements of prototyping. This mix of tools created an iterative learning process that enabled the gradual refinement of interventions and ensured their relevance to institutional needs. Co-design workshops served as a central mechanism for open discussion and collaborative decision-making, allowing different user groups to articulate needs, share expectations and work together on shaping new procedures and training materials.

AUTH also developed and prototyped training formats, workflow templates and tools supporting Open Science and open data sharing. Testing these prototypes in practice allowed teams to observe how the resources functioned within real institutional conditions, gather feedback, and adjust design elements before formal integration into existing research and administrative workflows.

This blended approach, combining exploratory and validation-oriented methods, provided both contextual insight and practical evidence. It enabled AUTH to understand challenges early, refine methods iteratively and ensure that the final outputs were realistic, user-centered and well aligned with the day-to-day working conditions of researchers and administrative staff.

Orchestration

AUTH demonstrated clear and effective orchestration of its transformation activities, coordinated through a dedicated working group composed of academic staff, administrative personnel and higher management. Leadership provided strategic direction, while roles and responsibilities were distributed according to each member's expertise, creating a collaborative structure that supported both operational efficiency and institutional ownership. Regular meetings, alongside the use of shared documents and digital communication channels, helped maintain alignment across units and ensured that all actors were informed and engaged throughout the process.

This coordinated approach facilitated transparent decision-making, steady progress and strong collaboration between academic and administrative units. The external

evaluation highlighted the coherence of this orchestration model, while noting that expanding engagement with external stakeholders could further enhance the broader impact of the transformation. Importantly, the governance structure established through the Acting Living Lab has the potential to remain in place beyond the project, providing a sustainable mechanism to continue supporting research culture and Open Science initiatives at AUTH.

Real-Life Setting

The real-life setting attribute was strongly present in AUTH's Acting Living Lab, with transformation actions implemented directly within teaching, research and administrative environments. Activities were tested through the Living Lab structures as well as through everyday academic workflows, allowing new procedures, training formats and tools to be trialed in the same contexts where they would eventually be adopted. This practical embedding enabled the team to observe how interventions functioned in real institutional conditions, identify what worked effectively, and adjust aspects that required refinement. It also enhanced stakeholder engagement by demonstrating tangible value and immediate applicability.

While challenges such as time constraints and varying levels of readiness across departments occasionally slowed progress, communication and the use of phased, adaptive implementation strategies helped maintain momentum. Overall, working in real-life settings ensured that the solutions developed were realistic, context-sensitive and more likely to be sustained beyond the project.

Co-creation

Co-creation was embedded throughout AUTH's Acting Living Lab, with internal stakeholders and selected external partners jointly shaping recognition frameworks, training materials and Open Science mechanisms. Through co-design workshops, joint planning sessions, stakeholders engaged in shared decision-making and contributed directly to the development of practical solutions, such as new training formats, workflow templates and procedures supporting Open Science and data sharing. This collaborative approach strengthened mutual learning, fostered collective ownership of the outcomes, and built long-term commitment to the transformation process. By ensuring that interventions were shaped by those who would ultimately use and implement them, AUTH increased the relevance, feasibility, and sustainability of the changes beyond the duration of the project.

4.8 CROSS-CASE REFLECTIONS

Across the seven Acting Living Labs, the evaluation shows that the six Living Lab attributes were interpreted and implemented in ways that are both consistent with the CATALISI objectives and sensitive to each institution's specific context. While the thematic focus of the transformation pathways varied—from research funding

sustainability and talent circulation to research assessment, research integrity, Open Science, citizen science and campus sustainability—the attribute-based analysis reveals clear patterns of convergence, as well as areas where methodological development can be further strengthened.

Active user involvement is the attribute that emerges as the most systematically and robustly applied across all Acting Living Labs. In every HEI, key user groups—including researchers at different career stages, PhD candidates, academic and administrative staff, and in some cases clinicians or school communities—were not only consulted but actively engaged in shaping priorities, co-designing actions, and testing early outputs. In several cases (UCC, KTU, UG, AUMC, AUTH), users directly influenced the redefinition of action plans, the design of training formats and support services, or the adjustment of procedures based on real experiences. Differences mainly concern the style of participation: some institutions experimented with highly interactive and creative formats, while others embedded user involvement in more formal decision-making and committee processes. Nevertheless, the overall trend points to a solid shift from tokenistic consultation towards more substantive and iterative involvement of users in institutional change.

The analysis of **multi-stakeholder participation** reveals a nuanced picture. In all seven HEIs, academia constitutes the core stakeholder group, which is consistent with the project's focus on institutional transformation and internal capacity building. However, several Acting Living Labs managed to extend participation to other components of the Quadruple Helix—industry, civil society, and public authorities—especially where the transformation topics were naturally outward facing, such as public engagement, citizen science, intellectual property, campus sustainability or Third Mission activities (notably UG, KTU, UCC and AUTH). By contrast, in transformation areas that are highly technical or governance-driven—such as research assessment, research integrity or internal ethics procedures (e.g. UJI, AUMC, parts of LUISS)—multi-stakeholder participation remained predominantly internal, with targeted contributions from external experts where relevant. This suggests that the depth and breadth of multi-stakeholder participation are strongly shaped by the nature of the transformation domain, and that external engagement is most effective where societal interfaces are explicit in the Action Plans.

Regarding the **multi-method approach**, all Acting Living Labs demonstrate a high degree of methodological maturity. Each institution used a combination of methods—such as surveys, interviews, workshops, focus groups, desk research, benchmarking, prototyping, and in some cases more innovative techniques like theatre-based sessions—to generate insights and steer decision-making. The specific configurations differed: some HEIs emphasized quantitative tools to capture patterns and levels of awareness, while others relied more intensively on qualitative and participatory methods to explore culture, norms and lived experiences. What they share, however, is an iterative logic: early evidence was used to refine actions, test prototypes, and adjust priorities. This confirms that the multi-method attribute is not merely about

diversity of tools but about combining them in a way that supports learning, triangulation of findings and progressive refinement of institutional interventions.

In terms of **orchestration**, all seven institutions put in place coordination mechanisms linking the Acting LL activities to their governance structures, yet they did so through distinct organizational models. Some HEIs (UCC, KTU, LUISS, UG, AUTH) relied on clearly identifiable coordination teams or working groups, often anchored in central offices or faculty leadership, with well-defined roles and regular communication routines. Others operated through more distributed governance systems, where multiple committees and units jointly steered the process (as in UJI), or embedded orchestration within a newly established permanent structure dedicated to research culture and integrity (as in AUMC's RIOS Centre). Across these variations, orchestration generally ensured alignment with institutional strategies, supported cross-unit collaboration, and created conditions for continuity beyond the lifespan of CATALISI. At the same time, the evaluation indicates that some HEIs could further strengthen the visibility and explicit framing of the "Acting Living Lab" as a coherent architecture, especially where governance structures are complex, and responsibilities widely distributed.

The **real-life setting** attribute is strongly present across all Acting LLs and constitutes one of their most distinctive strengths. Transformation actions were consistently implemented within authentic institutional environments: research support workflows, strategic planning processes, assessment and ethics committees, supervision practices, classrooms, laboratories, company collaborations, school partnerships and campus operations. Rather than designing parallel or purely experimental structures, the HEIs used existing systems as testbeds, allowing them to observe how interventions functioned under real conditions, how stakeholders responded, and which constraints or enablers became visible in practice. This grounding in everyday routines increased the realism and feasibility of the measures, supported incremental adjustments based on concrete experience and laid the foundations for long-term institutional uptake.

Finally, **co-creation** emerges as a central but differently articulated attribute across the seven cases. In some institutions, co-creation took highly visible and explicitly labelled forms, such as co-creation workshops, stakeholder labs, joint design sessions and creative formats (e.g. UG's co-creation around the Citizen Science Lab, KTU's co-design for mobility and writing support, UCC's strategic co-creation framework, AUMC's theatre-based collaborative reflection, AUTH's co-design workshops on recognition and Open Science). In others, co-creation was more embedded in governance and procedural work—for example, through joint drafting of policies, iterative consultations in committees and working groups, and collaborative refinement of guidelines and frameworks, even when not explicitly described as "co-creation" (as at UJI and parts of LUISS). Across both approaches, stakeholders contributed substantively to shaping institutional tools and processes, though there remains room in some HEIs to make the co-creation dimension more visible, to

formalize it as a recognized practice and to leverage it more systematically in external-facing activities.

Overall, the cross-case analysis indicates that the Acting Living Labs have significantly advanced the application of the six Living Lab attributes within Higher Education Institutions. They have helped experiment and normalize more participatory, evidence-informed and iterative ways of designing and implementing institutional change, and engaging in more open research and innovation processes, approaches which, according to several Implementers, were at times entirely new and contrasted with more protective, siloed and non-collaborative ways of working traditionally reinforced by the competitive nature of the academic environment. The analysis also reveals where further development is needed—for example, in more systematically integrating external stakeholders where this is thematically relevant, clarifying LL architectures within complex governance systems and explicitly connecting attribute-based evaluation to institutional learning cycles. These common trends provide an essential bridge to the next chapters, which examine the main achievements in terms of institutional change and formulate recommendations for future replicability and scaling of the Living Lab approach within and beyond the CATALISI partnership.

5. INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION: MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS OBSERVED ACROSS CATALISI ACTING LIVING LABS

The evaluation of the seven Acting Living Labs highlights a set of shared achievements that go beyond the delivery of individual Action Plan outputs. The Acting Living Labs contributed to tangible institutional change while also strengthening the capacity of HEIs to manage transformation in a more participatory, structured and sustainable way. The main achievements observed across cases are closely interlinked and can be grouped into five overarching areas.

Anchoring Institutional Change through Senior Leadership Endorsement

One of the most significant achievements across the Acting Living Labs was the ability to anchor transformation efforts structurally when senior leadership actively endorsed the direction of the work. Where rectoral teams, vice-rectors or faculty leadership supported the Acting Living Lab process, institutions were better positioned to ensure continuity, legitimacy and long-term integration of the changes introduced.

Senior leadership endorsement enabled Acting Living Lab outcomes to move beyond pilot initiatives and become embedded in institutional strategies, policies, and governance frameworks. For example, at AUTH, rectoral support helped integrate mobility, Open Science, and public engagement initiatives into faculty-level

strategies, strengthening their institutional visibility and sustainability. At UJI, validation at governance level was critical in anchoring new frameworks for research assessment and Open Science, ensuring alignment with formal decision-making structures and reducing the risk of fragmentation.

Across the consortium, leadership support proved essential for legitimizing participatory processes, facilitating cross-unit collaboration, and ensuring that the outcomes of the Acting Living Labs could influence institutional structures rather than remain isolated project-based interventions.

The Role of Strong and Cohesive Working Teams

A second key achievement was the presence of small, committed, and cohesive working teams that acted as the operational backbone of the Acting Living Labs. In all seven HEIs, progress was driven not by large formal structures, but by motivated core teams capable of translating strategic ambitions into concrete actions. These teams typically consisted of a core group of internal actors directly involved in CATALISI—such as academic leads, project coordinators and research support staff—but extended beyond the formal CATALISI teams to include representatives from key institutional units relevant to each Action Plan, including research offices, libraries, ethics committees, quality units, teaching, and learning centres.

These teams played a critical role in coordinating stakeholders, facilitating co-creation activities, maintaining momentum across implementation phases, and adapting actions in response to emerging insights. For instance, at the University of Gdańsk (UG), a core team of three to four members drove the development of the Citizen Science Lab, student engagement activities and collaborations with schools and businesses. At AUMC, a dedicated research culture group sustained momentum around research integrity, supervision training and educational innovation, ensuring continuity across multiple years.

The effectiveness of these teams demonstrates that institutional transformation does not necessarily require large new units, but rather clearly mandated teams with sufficient autonomy, facilitation capacity and institutional trust to operate across boundaries.

Broad Stakeholder Engagement as a Driver of Ownership and Embedding

A third major achievement concerns the depth and quality of stakeholder engagement achieved through the Acting Living Labs. When researchers, students, administrative staff and, where relevant, external partners from across the quadruple helix—actively contributed to shaping interventions, the resulting actions were more widely understood, accepted, and embedded. External partners included, for example, industry and business representatives involved in co-designing applied research activities and commissioned theses, public authorities and policy actors contributing to governance-related reforms, schools and educational organisations engaged in outreach and citizen science initiatives, and civil society

organisations and community actors participating in public engagement and open science activities.

Across the consortium, stakeholder engagement increased ownership and reduced resistance to change, as participants could see their contributions reflected in tangible outcomes. This was evident, for example, at AUTH, where the development of writing support services and mobility-related actions benefitted from close collaboration between academic staff and administrative units. At KTU, multiple institutional actors, such as researchers, doctoral candidates, library and research support staff, teaching units and central management representatives, contributed to the co-development of Open Science training formats and Living Lab-related educational components, strengthening internal alignment and uptake.

Even in cases where multi-stakeholder participation remained primarily internal due to the nature of the transformation areas (such as research assessment or research integrity), the structured involvement of diverse internal actors fostered a shared understanding of challenges and collective responsibility for solutions.

Alignment with National and European Policy Frameworks

Progress across the Acting Living Labs was further reinforced when institutional priorities aligned with broader national and European reform agendas. Alignment with policy frameworks such as Open Science, responsible research assessment, CoARA, citizen science and research integrity provided additional legitimacy, urgency, and coherence to the transformation processes.

This alignment helped institutions frame their internal changes as part of wider systemic developments rather than isolated reforms. For example, at UJI, the connection between the Acting Living Lab actions and European-level discussions on research assessment and Open Science, such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA), Open Science policies and evolving evaluation standards, strengthened institutional momentum and facilitated governance-level buy-in. Similar dynamics were observed in other HEIs where European policy developments provided a shared reference point for internal stakeholders.

By positioning Acting Living Lab activities within these broader reform movements, HEIs were able to mobilise support more effectively and create a clearer narrative around the purpose and relevance of institutional change.

Building on Existing Structures Rather than Creating Parallel Ones

Finally, a crucial achievement across the consortium was the decision to build on existing institutional structures instead of creating new, parallel units. By embedding Acting Living Lab actions within established services, committees, curricula, and support systems, HEIs increased the likelihood that changes would be sustained beyond the project.

This approach reduced organizational friction and facilitated integration into everyday workflows. For example, at AUTH, the university expanded and strengthened the existing Writing Clinic rather than creating a new training unit. At KTU, Living Lab

processes and training activities were integrated directly into existing academic procedures and curricula. Similar patterns were observed in other institutions, where Action Plan outputs were deliberately aligned with ongoing initiatives and structures.

Working through existing systems made transformation more feasible, reduced duplication and helped institutional actors perceive the changes as enhancements to current practices rather than additional burdens.

6. CHALLENGES ACROSS CATALISI ACTING LIVING LABS

While the Acting Living Labs proved effective in supporting institutional transformation across the seven HEIs, the implementation of the Action Plans also revealed a set of recurring challenges. These challenges were not specific to individual institutions but emerged as common patterns across contexts, reflecting the structural and organisational realities of higher education institutions undergoing change. They are summarized below.

Administrative Procedures and Formal Approval Processes

A first recurring challenge concerned the complexity of administrative procedures and the time required for formal approvals. Many of the transformation actions developed through the Acting Living Labs involved changes to institutional policies, guidelines, governance frameworks or internal procedures. As a result, these actions had to pass through multiple validation layers, including committees, boards and senior management structures.

This was particularly evident in cases such as AUTH and UJI, where actions related to mobility, public engagement, Open Science or research assessment required formal agreement at faculty or rectoral level. While these approval processes are an essential component of institutional governance and ensure legitimacy and long-term embedding, they also extended implementation timelines and limited the pace at which some actions could be fully operationalized. This challenge reflects the inherent tension between participatory experimentation and the procedural requirements of institutional change.

Limited Time and Overlapping Responsibilities of Implementation Teams

A second common challenge related to the limited availability of the teams responsible for implementing the Action Plans. In most cases, the same individuals leading the Acting Living Labs were also engaged in core teaching, research, administrative duties, and time-bound, externally funded transformation projects, including other European or national initiatives.

This overlap of responsibilities and role overload in HEIs sometimes created bottlenecks in implementation and slowed down the progression of activities. At UG, for example, the small core team driving the Citizen Science Lab and student engagement actions were simultaneously involved in several institutional initiatives,

requiring careful prioritization and sequencing of tasks. Similar dynamics were observed in other HEIs, where highly motivated but small teams carried a significant share of the transformation workload. This highlights the challenge of sustaining momentum when institutional transformation relies heavily on limited human resources and where the same people who drive innovation and change are also those already stretched across teaching, research, and administrative activities.

Engaging External Stakeholders in Institution-Centered Transformation Processes

Engaging external stakeholders represented an additional challenge across several Acting Living Labs. Although the Living Lab methodology encourages Quadruple Helix collaboration, many of the Action Plans focused on internal governance, institutional procedures and policy frameworks—such as research assessment reform, Open Science implementation or ethics committee processes—which inherently required deep internal knowledge and alignment.

In cases such as UJI and KTU, external stakeholders were consulted or involved selectively for benchmarking, validation or contextual insights, but could not meaningfully participate in sustained co-creation processes due to the highly specialised and internal nature of the transformation areas. Other institutions, including LUISS and AUTH, engaged external actors more actively within Third Mission or public engagement activities, but external involvement remained uneven across the full range of actions.

This challenge reflects a structural tension between the ambition for broad stakeholder engagement and the practical requirements of institution-centred transformation, where internal coordination and governance alignment are often prerequisites for meaningful external collaboration. It also highlights capacity-related constraints within HEIs, particularly in relation to systematically mapping, engaging, and sustaining relationships with external stakeholders. Several Implementers noted that effective external engagement depends on the availability of dedicated support structures—such as research support offices, innovation or knowledge transfer units, public engagement teams or existing networks with industry and policy actors—which are unevenly developed across institutions. Where such capacities were limited, external stakeholder engagement tended to remain ad hoc or project-specific, reinforcing the need to strengthen institutional infrastructures and skills for long-term, strategic collaboration beyond individual Living Lab cycles.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE REPLICABILITY

The experience of the seven CATALISI Acting Living Labs demonstrates that the Living Lab methodology can function as a powerful acceleration mechanism for institutional transformation when it is appropriately adapted to the realities of Higher Education Institutions. The evaluation findings highlight not only what has been achieved through CATALISI, but also how HEIs can build on this experience to sustain

and replicate Living Lab practices beyond the project's duration. The recommendations presented below synthesize lessons learned from the CATALISI implementers, insights from the external evaluation, and good practices emerging from the broader ENoLL Living Lab network, including the outcomes of the co-creation workshop on external stakeholder engagement organised during Open Living Lab Days 2024.

Embed Living Lab practices within institutional governance structures

A first and critical recommendation concerns the embedding of Living Lab practices within institutional governance structures. Across CATALISI, the most durable and impactful changes were observed where Acting Living Lab outcomes were translated into formal institutional artefacts such as action plans, policies, guidelines, frameworks, or recognition mechanisms. In these cases, Living Lab activities moved beyond project-based experiments and became integrated into routine institutional decision-making.

For successful replicability, HEIs should ensure that Living Lab cycles are explicitly connected to existing governance processes, including strategic planning, quality assurance, research support and training structures. This requires clear endorsement from senior leadership and recognition of co-creation and participatory approaches as legitimate and valuable components of institutional transformation.

Crucially, institutional embedding should be accompanied by the allocation of dedicated resources. This includes earmarking funding, staff time and operational support for participatory processes, co-creation activities and stakeholder engagement beyond the lifespan of externally funded projects. Without such resourcing, Living Lab practices risk remaining episodic rather than becoming structurally embedded.

In parallel, HEIs are encouraged to identify and empower internal roles or teams capable of facilitating Living Lab processes autonomously, building on the capacities developed during CATALISI. This may include research support staff, innovation or engagement officers, teaching and learning units, or academic champions trained in Living Lab facilitation. Developing internal facilitation capacity reduces long-term dependency on external actors and enables HEIs to deploy Living Lab methodologies flexibly and sustainably in response to emerging institutional needs.

Embedding Living Lab practices within governance systems—supported by adequate resourcing and internal facilitation capacity—strengthens legitimacy, enables continuity and significantly increases the likelihood that Living Lab outcomes will be sustained and scaled beyond individual projects.

Strengthen internal capacities for facilitation and co-creation

The evaluation highlights that Living Lab methodologies demand specific skills and competencies that are not yet widespread within HEIs. Effective facilitation,

stakeholder orchestration, participatory design and reflexive evaluation are central to the quality and impact of Living Lab processes, yet they often rely on a small number of motivated individuals.

To support replicability, HEIs should invest in building internal capacities through targeted training programmes, peer-learning formats and communities of practice focused on Living Lab methodologies. Developing methodological literacy among both academic and administrative staff will reduce dependency on external facilitators, enable distributed ownership across faculties and departments, and allow institutions to apply Living Lab approaches more flexibly to future transformation challenges.

Systematise and professionalise external stakeholder engagement strategies

External stakeholder engagement emerged as one of the most strategic ambitions of the Acting Living Labs, but also as one of the most complex and challenging dimensions. While all participating HEIs recognized the importance of engaging companies, public authorities, schools, NGOs, civil society organizations and community actors, many faced difficulties related to communication, alignment of priorities and the efficient use of limited resources.

To address these challenges, CATALISI organized a dedicated co-creation workshop on external stakeholder engagement during Open Living Lab Days 2024. The recommendations below are directly grounded in the outcomes of this workshop and reflect good practices from the ENOLL Living Lab network.

A first key lesson is the need for **structured and intentional communication**. Effective engagement should begin with systematic stakeholder mapping and analysis, identifying relevant actors and categorising them according to their influence, interest, and potential contribution. Tailored communication strategies should then be developed for different stakeholder groups, using accessible language, and avoiding academic jargon. Language and translation barriers were identified as significant obstacles, particularly for community-based or international stakeholders, and should be proactively addressed to ensure inclusivity.

Building trust through active listening is essential. External engagement should be based on transparent dialogue, regular updates and clear feedback loops that show stakeholders how their input is used. One-off consultations are rarely sufficient to sustain engagement; instead, continuous communication and visible follow-up are required to reinforce credibility and long-term collaboration.

A second lesson concerns **alignment on priorities and value propositions**. Engagement is more effective when mutual goals are clarified from the outset and when the value of participation is explicit for all parties. External stakeholders should be involved early in defining the problems or challenges to be addressed, rather than being invited only at validation stages. This collaborative problem definition increases commitment and ensures that Living Lab activities respond to real needs.

Alignment should be treated as an iterative process. Regular needs assessments, check-ins and validation moments allow HEIs to adapt activities to evolving stakeholder priorities and maintain relevance throughout the Living Lab cycle.

A third lesson relates to **strategic resource utilisation**. Given capacity constraints, HEIs should explicitly leverage the university itself as a Living Lab by mobilizing existing internal expertise, infrastructures, and activities rather than creating parallel engagement structures. Where possible, this should be supported by the formalization or strengthening of dedicated institutional units or offices responsible for external engagement, such as research support offices, innovation and technology transfer offices, public engagement units or Living Lab coordination functions. Having clearly mandated structures with defined roles and responsibilities helps institutionalize engagement practices and provides continuity beyond individual projects.

Stakeholder mapping should inform differentiated engagement strategies, allocating more intensive co-creation efforts to high-priority stakeholders while using lighter engagement mechanisms for others. The workshop also highlighted the importance of Open Science and technology transfer as enablers of engagement. Sharing research outputs, data and innovations creates tangible entry points for collaboration, while internal training on stakeholder engagement, Open Science and technology transfer can empower departments to engage more effectively. Finally, regular evaluation of engagement activities—using both qualitative and quantitative indicators—helps optimize resource use and demonstrate impact.

Taken together, these lessons underline that external stakeholder engagement must be treated as a strategic, professionalized function rather than an ad hoc project activity. By systematizing communication, aligning priorities, and managing resources deliberately, HEIs can build resilient collaboration ecosystems that support long-term institutional transformation.

Align Living Lab cycles with institutional rhythms and constraints

Several Acting Living Labs encountered challenges related to timing, particularly where co-creation cycles did not align with academic calendars, governance procedures or administrative approval processes. These misalignments occasionally delayed implementation and reduced the immediate impact of participatory activities.

For future replication, HEIs should anticipate institutional rhythms early and adapt the sequencing of Living Lab activities accordingly. Aligning Living Lab phases with key decision-making moments, committee schedules and workload peaks increase the likelihood that participatory processes can meaningfully inform institutional decisions rather than running in parallel to them.

Invest in communication and visibility as enablers of sustainability

The evaluation demonstrates that Living Lab initiatives gain legitimacy and momentum when their progress and outcomes are visible internally and externally. Institutions that actively communicated about Living Lab activities—through newsletters, internal presentations, events and participation in networks—were more successful in sustaining engagement and embedding outcomes.

For replicability, HEIs should adopt communication strategies that highlight not only final outputs but also the co-creation process itself, the contributions of stakeholders and the institution's commitment to participatory transformation. Visibility strengthens institutional buy-in, attracts new participants and reinforces Living Labs as credible instruments for change.

Clarify the role and scope of Acting Living Labs within HEIs

Some institutions initially experienced ambiguity in distinguishing Acting Living Lab processes from other forms of consultation or project activity. This occasionally led to confusion around roles, expectations, and outcomes.

To support replicability, HEIs should clearly define the purpose, scope, and governance of Acting Living Labs before launching new cycles. Clarifying how Living Labs differ from traditional working groups or consultations improves coordination, manages expectations and positions Living Labs as strategic transformation instruments rather than isolated workshops.

Integrate monitoring, learning and evaluation from the outset

The evaluation highlights the value of continuous reflection and learning within Living Lab processes. Acting Living Labs that integrated feedback mechanisms, satisfaction assessments and reflective moments were better able to adapt activities in real time and demonstrate value to institutional leadership.

For future replication, HEIs should embed simple but robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms from the outset. These practices support adaptive learning, strengthen internal advocacy, and generate evidence that can be used to justify continued investment in Living Lab approaches.

Reinforce the experimental and innovation-oriented dimension of Living Labs

In line with the EAB evaluation, the findings suggest that some Acting Living Labs focused heavily on governance and descriptive processes, while the experimental dimension of the Living Lab methodology could be further strengthened. Future cycles would benefit from more explicit experimentation, prototyping and real-life testing of solutions.

Integrating pilots, scenario-based exploration or experimental formats reinforces the distinctiveness of the Living Lab approach and enhances its transformative potential.

Foster a long-term institutional culture of co-creation and openness

Finally, the sustainability of Living Lab practices depends on cultural change. While projects like CATALISI can catalyze transformation, embedding participatory and co-creative principles requires sustained institutional commitment over time.

HEIs should use the momentum generated by the Acting Living Labs to integrate openness, shared responsibility and collaboration into everyday practices, recognition systems and institutional narratives. When co-creation becomes part of how universities routinely design policies, services and strategies, Living Labs can continue to function as powerful engines of institutional learning and innovation.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of the seven Acting Living Labs demonstrates that the Living Lab methodology can function not only as a project-based intervention, but as a strategic acceleration mechanism for institutional transformation in Higher Education Institutions. Rather than representing isolated experimentation, the Acting Living Labs enabled HEIs to rehearse new ways of organizing change through participation, real-life testing and iterative learning, while operating within existing governance arrangements, resource constraints and academic cultures.

Looking ahead, the analysis suggests that Acting Living Labs have strong potential to be scaled up and institutionalized within Higher Education Institutions, provided that enabling conditions such as leadership endorsement, internal capacities and alignment with governance processes are in place. Instead of remaining confined to project-based experimentation, Acting Living Labs could evolve into permanent or semi-permanent institutional mechanisms applied across multiple research and innovation domains, including research assessment reform, Open Science, research careers, public engagement and sustainability transitions. This potential aligns closely with evolving European policy frameworks, including the European Research Area, CoARA and Open Science agendas.

This forward-looking potential is supported by evidence from the evaluation survey conducted by UCC as part of the assessment of CATALISI acceleration services, in which the Living Lab methodology was ranked among the highest-rated services in terms of utilization, perceived usefulness and reproducibility. This result reinforces the conclusion that the Living Lab approach is not only methodologically robust, but is also perceived by Implementers as a practical, transferable, and value-creating mechanism for institutional transformation.

The evaluation further highlights that successful scaling does not depend on the uniform replication of structures or activities. Instead, it relies on embedding core Living Lab principles such as co-creation, multi-stakeholder engagement, real-life experimentation, and adaptive orchestration within existing institutional systems. HEIs that aligned Living Lab activities with governance processes, strategic planning cycles and recognized policy frameworks were better positioned to sustain momentum over time. This underscores the importance of anchoring Living Lab approaches within institutional mandates rather than relying solely on project teams or external facilitation.

From a European policy perspective, the findings position Acting Living Labs as a concrete delivery mechanism for ERA priorities. The work carried out across the seven HEIs contributes directly to objectives related to the ERA Policy Agenda, the Pact for Research and Innovation, and the implementation of frameworks such as CoARA,

Open Science policies and Responsible Research and Innovation. By translating high-level policy commitments into participatory institutional processes, Acting Living Labs help bridge the gap between European ambitions and operational change within universities.

At the same time, the evaluation underscores that scaling Living Lab approaches requires intentional investment in institutional capacity. Challenges related to administrative procedures, limited staff time and uneven experience with stakeholder engagement are structural realities of institutional transformation and will not be resolved through replication alone. Future deployment of Living Labs within HEIs would benefit from clearer resource allocation, dedicated facilitation roles and stronger internal coordination mechanisms, potentially supported by formal engagement or innovation offices capable of sustaining Living Lab cycles autonomously.

Taken together, the legacy of the CATALISI Acting Living Labs lies less in the individual actions implemented and more in the institutional capabilities that were strengthened. By enabling universities to experiment with new forms of governance, participation and learning, the Acting Living Labs have laid the groundwork for continued transformation beyond the project. In this sense, Living Labs emerge not as temporary project tools, but as transferable and adaptable institutional assets for Higher Education Institutions navigating complex, policy-driven change within the European Research Area.

ANNEX 1- SURVEY ON THE ACTION PLAN IMPLEMENTATION AND THE APPLICATION OF THE LIVING LAB METHODOLOGY

CATALISI_Evaluation of Action Plan Implementation & the Living Lab Acceleration Service

15/12/2025 18:30

CATALISI_Evaluation of Action Plan Implementation & the Living Lab Acceleration Service

This survey aims to collect feedback from HEIs-Implementers on the 1st wave of action plan implementation and the Living Lab acceleration service. It focuses on understanding successes and any revisions made to the action plans. Additionally, the survey assesses the Living Lab acceleration service against core Living Lab principles such as user

Consent and Identification

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2. First Name *

3. Last Name *

4. E-mail *

5. Organisation *

9. Action Plan Revision Following the initial implementation phase, action plans were revised by CATALISI HEIs for different reasons, which could eventually include shifting priorities, updated timelines, or the need to make them more concrete and impactful in driving institutional transformation.

- What prompted the revisions to your action plans?
- Which activities were revised, and if applicable, could you explain the rationale for prioritizing certain actions over others?

*

Section 1: Action Plan Implementation

6. **Achievements** Describe the main achievements of the first wave of implementation of your action plans *

7. **Alignment with Institutional Transformation Goals**

- Are the actions impacting your transformational pathways? if so, in which ways?
- How can the Coaching Service better support you in aligning your action plan goals with the Institutional Transformation Goals?

*

8. **Key Learnings and Good Practices** Describe valuable insights or good practices that could benefit future actions

*

Section 2: LL Acceleration Service Evaluation

10. Stakeholder Updates and Feedback Integration

- How are you keeping your stakeholders informed about the progress of implementation? Engagement can involve sharing updates, seeking feedback, or other forms of communication, such as emails or meetings.
- Have you incorporated any feedback from stakeholders into the revision of your action plans, whether from the validation survey sent after the second round of workshops or from any other recent meetings?

11. Tools and Methods for Engagement

- Which tools and methods for engagement have you used AND plan to use with your stakeholders?

12. Challenges and Support Needs

- What are the main challenges you have encountered in engaging with stakeholders?
- What additional support do you require from ENOLL to improve stakeholder engagement and co-creation?

*

13. Stakeholder engagement and co-creation- Next activities

- Maintaining stakeholder engagement is essential to ensure their involvement in your institutional transformation journey. Based on your activities, and expected results, could you please list the next engagement activities you see as relevant for 2025? These could include communication efforts, in-person or online workshops, surveys, or other methods to keep stakeholders informed and consider their feedback

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ANNEX 2- FINAL SURVEY ON THE ACTION PLAN IMPLEMENTATION AND THE APPLICATION OF THE LIVING LAB METHODOLOGY

Final Survey on the Implementation of Action Plans and the Application of the LL Methodology

15/12/2025 18:46

Final Survey on the Implementation of Action Plans and the Application of the LL Methodology

This survey aims to collect final feedback from CATALISI Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) on the second phase of Action Plan implementation and the application of the Living Lab (LL) methodology. It seeks to capture the main progress and outcomes achieved during the full implementation period. to assess how the Living Lab approach has been applied across its

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3. Last Name *

4. E-mail *

5. Organisation *

Implementation of the Second Phase of Action Plans

This section focuses on assessing the final progress, institutional impact, and lessons learned achieved during the full implementation phase of the Action Plans. It invites Higher Education Institutions to reflect on how their planned actions were carried out, what tangible results and changes were observed, and what insights emerged from the process. The objective is to capture both the achievements and the challenges encountered in implementing the transformation pathways, provid-

6. **Overview of Actions and Status**• Please provide a brief overview of your Action Plan implementation at this stage: Which actions have been completed, which are still in progress, and which are planned or upcoming beyond the project timeline? If possible, please specify the key results or milestones achieved for each main action. *

7. **Timeline and Delays**. Was the implementation timeline followed as planned? .If there were any delays or rescheduling, please explain the reasons (e.g. administrative, institutional, contextual, or resource-related) and how they were managed. *

8. Institutional Transformation• What concrete institutional transformations (strategic, operational, or cultural) have resulted from the implementation of your Action Plan? How sustainable do you consider these changes after the end of the project? *

9. Enablers, Challenges, and Lessons Learned• What were the main factors that facilitated your progress (leadership, teamwork, partnerships, resources, etc.)?•What challenges did you face, and how were they addressed?•What are the key lessons learned from this overall implementation process that could support future replication? *

Evaluation of the Living Lab Methodology Application

This section aims to assess how effectively the Living Lab (LL) methodology was applied to support institutional transformation during the implementation of your Action Plan, based on the six ENoLL attribute areas. In the context of CATALISI, users refer to those directly affected by or contributing to institutional change — such as academic staff, administrative personnel, researchers, or students when transformation occurs within the institution, and external partners (public authorities, businesses, NGOs, citizens, etc.) when transformation relies on collaboration with the wider ecosystem. The Living Lab approach in CATALISI focuses on co-cre-

10. **Active User Involvement:** This criterion assesses how meaningfully users — whether internal (e.g. academic staff, administrative staff, researchers) or external (e.g. students, partners, stakeholders) — were engaged in shaping and implementing the institutional transformation process. It focuses on involving those directly affected by change in the design, testing, and validation of new approaches, services, or governance mechanisms. **Question:** How were users — internal and/or external — meaningfully involved in shaping and implementing your institutional transformation actions, including through activities such as participatory workshops, focus groups, testing sessions, or consultations, and how did their feedback influence the design and success of the process? *

11. Multi-Method Approach: This criterion assesses the extent to which your institution applied a variety of complementary methods to support the transformation process — for example, combining co-design workshops, data analysis, feedback loops, and experimentation to gather insights, test new ways of working, and strengthen results. **Question:** How did you combine different and complementary methods — such as co-design workshops, surveys, interviews, participatory mapping, or prototyping — to guide your institutional transformation, and how did this multi-method approach help you better understand

12. Multi-Stakeholder Participation: This criterion assesses how the institutional transformation process engaged stakeholders from the Quadruple Helix (QH) — encompassing academia, government/public authorities, industry/private sector, and civil society. It looks at both the representation of these groups and the quality of their participation, ensuring that transformation actions are co-created, inclusive, and reflective of diverse perspectives and interests. **Question:** How were stakeholders from the Quadruple Helix — including academia, government/public authorities, private sector, and civil society — represented and involved in co-developing and implementing your institutional transformation actions? Please indicate the approximate percentage representation of each stakeholder group (totaling 100%) and explain how their engagement contributed to balanced representation, shared ownership, and a more inclusive transformation process. *

13. Orchestration: This criterion assesses how the Higher Education Institution (HEI) coordinated and facilitated actors, resources, and activities to ensure coherence and continuity throughout the institutional transformation process. Orchestration refers to the leadership, communication mechanisms, and governance structures established by the HEI to align stakeholders around shared objectives. It involves managing roles and responsibilities, ensuring transparency in decision-making, and maintaining collaboration across internal units and external partners. **Question:** How did your institution orchestrate the transformation process — in terms of leadership, coordination structures, and communication mechanisms?

14. Real-Life Setting: This criterion assesses how the Higher Education Institution (HEI) tested and implemented its transformation actions within a real-life setting, meaning in authentic institutional contexts where activities, processes, and interactions naturally take place. Applying actions in real-life conditions allows the institution to observe how change unfolds in practice, engage directly with those involved, and adapt approaches based on concrete experiences and feedback. **Question:** How were your transformation actions tested and implemented in real-life settings, and how did this practical application help generate learning, adaptation, or tangible results within your institutional transformation journey? Please describe the main benefits and challenges of implementing actions in these real-life conditions. *

Integration of External Evaluation Feedback

This section aims to assess whether and how the feedback provided by the external experts as part of the CATALISI evaluation was taken into account during the final phase of implementation. In April 2025, external experts' feedback reports were shared with the Higher Education Institutions, namely Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC), Universitat Jaume I (UJI), Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), and University College Cork (UCC). Institutions that did not receive external feedback may skip this section.

17. Were the recommendations or comments from the external experts taken into account in your final implementation phase? If yes, please describe which feedback was integrated and how it influenced your institutional transformation process or specific activities. If not, please explain why this feedback was not incorporated (e.g. not relevant to your context, limited time/resources, strategic choice, institutional constraints).

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15. **Co-creation:** This criterion assesses how the Higher Education Institution (HEI) engaged relevant internal and external actors in jointly designing and deciding on transformation actions. Unlike the multi-method approach, which focuses on the diversity of tools used, co-creation focuses on the collaborative process itself — how different perspectives, experiences, and forms of expertise were brought together to define priorities, shape solutions, and ensure shared ownership of outcomes. **Question:** How did your institution apply co-creation in developing and implementing transformation actions? Please describe how internal and external actors worked together to design

16. Do you plan to continue applying the Living Lab methodology within your institution after CATALISI ends, and if so, in which areas (e.g. strategic planning, sustainability, digitalisation, partnerships, education)? Please also indicate what support or resources would be most helpful to sustain or scale up this approach. *

ANNEX 3- WEBINAR_CASE STUDY_UVT DIGITAL & GREEN LIVING LAB CASE STUDY

Concept Note

Session Title:

The Living Lab approach applied within the university setting

(UVT Digital & Green Living Lab Case Study)

Date: 21st March, 9:30 AM - 11:00 PM (CET)

Online

Session overview

This session will explore the UVT Digital & Green Living Lab as a case study, showcasing how UVT has successfully implemented the Living Lab approach to drive innovation, collaboration, and institutional transformation within a university setting.

Drawing from UVT's experience, the session will highlight the key processes, stakeholders, methods & tools that enable the university to act as a Living Lab. The discussion will focus on how Living Labs serve as catalysts for institutional transformation, fostering experimentation, co-creation, and real-world impact within university ecosystems. The objective is to provide practical insights into implementing Living Lab principles, helping universities become more adaptive, open, and impact-driven.

Conducted in an interview format, the session will offer a deep dive into best practices, key challenges, and lessons learned from UVT's journey in embedding the Living Lab approach within its university structure. Participants will also have the opportunity to engage with the speaker, ask questions, and exchange perspectives at the end of the session.

By leveraging the expertise of Living Lab practitioners, this session will provide actionable insights for universities seeking to adopt and scale the Living Lab methodology, making it a core component of their innovation and transformation strategies.

Expected Outcomes:

This session will provide participants with a practical understanding of how the Living Lab approach operates within a university setting. Through the UVT Digital & Green Living Lab case study, attendees will gain insights into the key processes and methodologies that enable universities to embed Living Labs effectively. The discussion will showcase real-world applications, demonstrating how Living Labs create experimental spaces for innovation, co-creation, and stakeholder collaboration.

This session aims to serve as a guide and inspiration for Higher Education Institutions to succeed meaningful transformative projects through the Living Lab.

The session will also offer an opportunity for engagement and knowledge exchange, allowing participants to connect with experts, ask questions, and explore strategies for integrating Living Labs into their innovation and transformation agendas.

Target Audience:

This session is primarily designed for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) within the CATALISI project, providing them with practical insights into the implementation of the Living Lab approach to support institutional transformation.

While the focus is on HEIs engaged in CATALISI, the session is also open to a broader audience, including university leaders, faculty, researchers, innovation managers, and Living Lab practitioners interested in leveraging this methodology for co-creation, collaboration, and impact-driven innovation within the academy. It will also be relevant to higher education policymakers and external stakeholders looking to understand how Living Labs can facilitate systemic change in academic environments.

Format

The session will be structured as an interactive discussion with a mix of thematic introduction, case study presentation (interview format), and audience engagement, ensuring a dynamic and insightful exchange.

- **Introduction to the Living Lab Approach & Institutional Transformation (20 min):**

The session will begin with an overview of the Living Lab methodology, its key principles, and its application within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). It will also introduce UVT Digital and Green Living Lab.

This segment will highlight how Living Labs support institutional transformation, foster innovation, and create impact-driven collaborations in university settings.

- **Case Study UVT Digital & Green Living Lab (40 min):**

The core of the session will feature an interview-style discussion with a representative from UVT, focusing on:

- **Origin:** How the Living Lab approach was implemented at UVT.
- **The University as a Living Lab:** Key processes, operational strategies, stakeholders
- **Challenges and Lessons Learned:** Challenges faced and lessons learned in applying the approach and the impact of the Living Lab on the institutional transformation.
- **Future Perspectives & Recommendations:** A set of recommendations to apply the Living Lab for Institutional transformation.

- **Interactive Discussion & Q&A (30 min):**

The session will conclude with a participant-driven discussion, where attendees can ask questions, share perspectives, and exchange insights with the speaker. This will provide an opportunity for peer learning and networking, fostering potential collaborations and deeper engagement with the Living Lab methodology in HEIs.

Interview Structure & Suggested Questions

1. The Origins How the Living Lab approach was implemented at UVT

- ✔ What inspired the creation of the UVT Digital & Green Living Lab? What challenges or needs led the university to adopt the Living Lab methodology?
- ✔ How did the idea gain support within the university? Who were the key stakeholders involved in the early stages?
- ✔ Were there any initial concerns or resistance, and how were they addressed?
- 💡 What interesting story can you share about the early days of setting up the Living Lab? Was there a turning point that made the initiative take off?

2. The University as a Living Lab (10 min)

- ✔ How has the university's internal culture evolved since implementing the Living Lab approach?
- ✔ What structural changes were needed to embed the Living Lab methodology within UVT?
- ✔ How did faculty, researchers, and students adapt to this new way of working?
- ✔ What role do external stakeholders (e.g., policymakers, businesses, communities) play in the Living Lab ecosystem?
- 💡 Can you share a real-life example of how the Living Lab has transformed the way the university operates or collaborates?

3. Challenges and Lessons Learned (10 min)

- ✔ What concrete outcomes or successes have emerged from the Living Lab approach at UVT?
- ✔ From the CATALISI experience some of the common challenges are around the external stakeholder engagement. Especially when the topics are very technical, or includes some research, for example. From your experience what can be done or used to boost the stakeholder's participation? Can you share a concrete action, or recommendation that be used by others?
- ✔ What have been the biggest challenges in maintaining and scaling the Living Lab? And how have you overcome these challenges?
- ✔ How do you measure success and ensure the sustainability of the Living Lab?
- 💡 Was there a particularly unexpected or inspiring moment where the Living Lab made a significant difference?

4. Future Perspectives & Recommendations (10 min)

- ✔ Based on your experience, what advice would you give to other universities looking to implement a Living Lab?
- ✔ How do you see the role of Living Labs evolving in higher education in the coming years?
- ✔ What are UVT's next steps in strengthening and expanding the Living Lab model?
- 💡 If you could go back to the beginning of this journey, what would you do differently?

ANNEX 4- WEBINAR_PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND OUTREACH

PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND OUTREACH

This webinar series offers Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) insights and strategies for institutional transformation, featuring expert speakers who share best practices, research findings, and actionable strategies.

[Register now!](#)

29TH MAY 2025
10:00-12:00

10:00 – 10:05

Introduction to the Webinar

EY

10:05 – 10:10

Introduction of CATALISI project

APRE

10:10 – 11:00

Public Engagement and Participatory Practices for stakeholder collaboration + Q&A

Ciara O'Halloran, Programme Officer, Research Culture, Engagement and Impact at University College Cork

11:00 – 11:50

Stakeholder's Engagement + Q&A

Mariem Chakroun, International Project Manager at ENoLL, Leidy Vanessa Enriquez Florez International Project Manager & Senior Event Manager at ENoLL.

11:50 – 12:00

Closing Remarks

EY

CIARA O'HALLORAN

Programme Officer, Research Culture, Engagement and Impact at University College Cork | Co-Creation Specialist, UNIC Centre for City Futures

MARIEM CHAKROUN

International Project Manager

LEIDY VANESSA ENRIQUEZ FLOREZ

International Project Manager & Senior Event Manager

ANNEX 5- WEBINAR_CO-DESIGN AS DRIVER OF ADAPTIVE AND LEARNING-ORIENTED INSTITUTIONS

CO-DESIGN AS A DRIVER OF ADAPTIVE AND LEARNING-ORIENTED INSTITUTIONS

This webinar series offers Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) insights and strategies for institutional transformation, featuring expert speakers who share best practices, research findings, and actionable strategies.

Webinar

11 Dec, 2025
10:00-12:00

[Register now!](#)

10:00 – 10:10

Welcome and Opening remarks

EY

10:10 – 10:15

Introduction of CATALISI project

APRE

10:15 – 11:00

Co-Creation Concept and Toolkit + Q&A

Mariem Chakroun

11:00 – 11:45

Co-design as a driver of adaptive and learning-oriented institutions + Q&A

Gioia Carbini

11:45 – 12:00

Closing Remarks

EY

MARIEM CHAKROUN

International Project
Manager at the European
Network of Living Labs
(ENoLL)

GIOIA CARBINI

Senior Manager at EY
(Ernst & Young)